

Inherit

Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements/D2.1

WP2, T 2.1

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Executive Summary

The overall vision behind the INHERIT project is to create a systematic methodology, accompanied by leading edge Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and (big) data analytics, and associated social/behavioural practices, towards sustainable, inclusive, and resource-efficient cultural heritage (CH) solutions.

INHERIT takes the social value of CH into account in order to enable innovative interventions at different urban levels like at buildings, at the neighbourhood, at the city or at the community covering relevant aspects of the heritage-built environment's life cycle. To achieve this, the INHERIT project fosters its CH building stock in the social context and intends to create opportunities for stakeholders in co-creation activities impacting local and regional ecosystems.

The purpose of this handbook, which is the deliverable 2.1 of the INHERIT project, is to present all approaches for co-creation and to delineate their underlying strategy and objectives to be achieved. In detail, the handbook provides the methodological framework and a hands-on pre-selection of approaches to cope with the site-specifics of the eight INHERIT pilots. The handbook starts with the initial phase of the co-creation process in INHERIT (M1-M8) and gives an outlook about its continuation over the full project runtime. Moreover, it describes social labs as the main research method and main setting for co-creation activities. In addition, the handbook explains the so-called Multi-Stakeholder Forum, which intends to develop a transregional and European community of interest of professionals and researchers to support the co-creation process with feedback.

The results displayed stem from a stakeholder mapping and several internal co-design activities, which were all pooled both into an overall and a site-specific engagement strategy tailored to the situation of each pilot. The handbook gives a comprehensive overview about the manifold activities already implemented in the first eight months of the project. Partially and where already known, it also touches upon those activities in the planning for the future of the project. This is made in the context of the INHERIT Social Life Cycle Assessment, the transfer of New European Bauhaus values into the work on the ground of INHERIT, the sensitive involvement of stakeholders as beta-users of INHERIT solutions and the development of user scenarios cooperatively with stakeholders, who will benefit the development of INHERIT's technical and technology related solutions for the CH sector with their user-centred perspective.

Technical references

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

ABBREVIATION	DEFINITION
AI	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
ABF	ARCHITECTE DES BÂTIMENTS DE FRANCE (FRANCE)
AEICE	CLÚSTER DE HÁBITAT EFICIENTE (SPAIN)
AoH	ART OF HOSTING
AR/VR	AUGMENTED REALITY/VIRTUAL REALITY
CH	CULTURAL HERITAGE
CCI	CULTURE AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES
CoC	CODE OF CONDUCT
CoI	COMMUNITY OF INTEREST
CSO	CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS
DT	DIGITAL TWIN
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
FAQ	FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT
GPS	GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEM
H-BIM	HERITAGE BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING
ICT	INFORMATION, COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES
IoT	INTERNET OF THINGS
ISO	INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION FOR STANDARDIZATION
MSF	MULTI-STAKEHOLDER FORUM
NEB	NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS
NGO	NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANISATION
OECD	THE ORGANISATION FOR ECONOMIC CO-OPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT
OOD	OPERATORS, OWNERS, DECISION-MAKERS
QH	QUADRUPLE-HELIX
S-LCA	SOCIAL-LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT
S-LCM	SOCIAL-LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT

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SSH	SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
STH	STAKEHOLDER
T	TASK
UI	USER INTERFACE
UNEP	UNITED NATIONS ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME
WP	WORK PACKAGE
ZBILK	SOCIAL BUILDINGS MANAGEMENT (POLAND)

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1. Introduction

Main research approaches, processes, preliminary results and reflections on further activities of INHERIT's co-creation and social lab journey are summarised in the *Social Labs Methodological Handbook, D2.1 high-level requirements* at hand.¹

The research and co-creation done in the INHERIT project aims to contribute to socially accepted retrofit concepts, socially responsible forms of reuse of CH and to the formation of more empowered communities. It builds a set of targeted as well as open-ended processes valorising the knowledge and creativity of multi-stakeholders for latest state-of-the-art technology and services that are meaningful to professional users and, whenever possible, to communities.

This handbook is addressed to

- experts of CH management and technology,
- communities and their representatives willing to participate in co-creation processes in the context of CH,
- representatives from cultural policy making and urban planning,
- and the INHERIT project consortium made up of an interdisciplinary team.

By establishing a tailor-made research and co-creation approach and by incorporating stakeholder feedback across the project lifetime, INHERIT can create new adaptive models of engagement and sets the scene for transdisciplinary collaboration. bringing together experts from information technology, smart energy performance, Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR), design and preservation, CH management and the social sciences and humanities (SSH).

The **deliverable** (D2.1) at hand puts this co-creation process centre stage in form of a handbook, presenting main approaches applied, such as the INHERIT social labs in eight pilots, the MSF and the S-LCA, the latter which is as an emerging approach in the field of CH research.

1.1. Underlying Definitions

In the context of INHERIT, a **social lab** can be understood as the main research approach and - at the same time – as a temporary collaborative space, where CH, sustainable concepts of use, the energy efficiency of CH buildings, the special features of the localities and social objectives intersect while harnessing the collective intelligence and creativity of multi-stakeholders to generate solutions that are more sustainable, socially responsible, and socially accepted. Following this idea,

¹ A figure describing the interdependencies between the tasks of WP 2 in the INHERIT project can be found in the Appendix.

the INHERIT social labs create a unique collaborative setting as an enabler to jointly work on site-specific social or socio-technological problems.

While INHERIT social labs address multi-stakeholders including also volunteer researcher with no specific expertise on CH, such as representatives from the local communities), the **Multi-Stakeholder Forum** (MSF) serves as a transregional platform to gain high-profile expert feedback and facilitates the dialogue among diverse expert stakeholders related to topics pre-defined by INHERIT consortium members. It aims to enable mutual learning between the INHERIT consortium and experts from practice and research. The forum also facilitates the exchange of innovative ideas, best practices, and lessons learned from other successful CH retrofit projects.

The third strategic instrument for the INHERIT co-creation process is the **S-LCA**, which is oriented towards the organisational governance level of the eight pilots. To carry out an assessment over time (before, in the mid and after the social lab process), it observes and relatedly measures changes in knowledge and expertise on the topic of inclusive cultural heritage management at the individual level of owners, operators and decision-makers of each pilot building, drawing on the triple bottom line of organisational performance including the social, environmental, and economic dimensions. In this context, the S-LCA provides a reference point for social responsibility and organisational behaviour in the pilots.

1.2. Main Activities, Expected Outcomes and Structure of the Handbook

The handbook casts light on preparatory activities, which have been carried out between the start of the project until the finalisation of this document (M1-M8) and gives an outlook on the co-creation activities in the social labs and the MSF over the full project lifetime.

Based on interim results gained in the introductory research and co-design phase, the handbook covers an initial stakeholder mapping with a context analysis for each pilot serving as the major basis for the individual engagement strategies for each pilot and the key approaches relevant to carrying out co-creation with multi-stakeholders from the Quadruple Helix (QH) including stakeholders from education/research, policymaking, industry and business and civil society. In addition, the handbook presents further preparatory activities between the project partners such as the co-design of the social labs and the MSF.

When it comes to starting the eight social labs with the first kick-off workshops, which are implemented between **M8-M11** of the project, the process enters its second phase, namely the engagement of local stakeholders on the ground.

The project aims to spark both, scientific and critical-creative reflection of the local space to boost participation in the INHERIT project. Participating stakeholders are further guided by local pilot partners, who draw on methodologies and approaches as outlined in **chapter 2, 3, 4 and 5** of this handbook. This joint endeavour, replicated in several workshop until **M39** and beyond, until the end of the INHERIT project, constitutes the participatory mode of the social labs and the MSF, bringing together multi-stakeholders with specific needs, interests, and knowledge.

The handbook presents the overall research process in the social context, suggests approaches and methods for the eight INHERIT pilots, and summarises preliminary results, which will be further refined during the co-creation process in INHERIT.

Figure 1: Main activities of the INHERIT co-creation process

1.3. Outlook On Chapter 1 To 9

After an **introduction** presenting underlying definitions as well as expected outcomes, the **chapter two** presents an analysis of relevant literature and best practice projects synthesised with the results of a series of exploratory interviews with pilot lead partners and a first stakeholder mapping. The information collected helps to build initial recruitment and engagement strategies, which is presented with in this handbook with practical information on how-to set up the social labs and the MSF.

This handbook also presents a framework and a plan about how to foster NEB values and working principles in the INHERIT pilots and how to make INHERIT pilots more accessible and inclusive from a social point of view. In a later phase of the project (**M14 – M37**), ongoing reflection on NEB will be

transferred into practice and into lab activities using a range of critical-creative research and co-creation approaches.²

The **third chapter** explains the social lab methodological handbook starting with a short description of the interplay of social labs, MSF and S-LCA as instruments for co-creation. Further the chapter explains main objectives, the conceptual design and two workshop methods suggested to be used during the kick-off lab events in the eight pilots. The toolkit, the code of conduct and the information on the lab seed money help to deal with practical issues for lab managers or hosts, moderators and facilitators of the social labs.

In **chapter four**, the MSF is described as the second instrument in INHERIT for collaborative, feedback and co-creation. The chapter presents a rationale, an outlook on the major phases and activities, the agenda setting, the general layout and more details concerning the MSF.

Chapter five explains the S-LCA as an important assessment tool, and the final chapter with an outlook on the work in user-centred testbeds for INHERIT solutions and user scenarios.

All activities and interventions stick to the INHERIT objective on creating long-term sustainability for the solutions developed, which are energy-efficient, transformative on the one, and socially inclusive, socially innovative, and socially responsible on the other hand. Firstly, the social labs as a constituent research method build important cross-disciplinary bridges to other activities. They are closely intertwined with the S-LCA implemented between **M1 – M39**. Thus, knowledge and experience transfer from the social labs to the S-LCA and vice versa by each stakeholder personally is likely to happen.

Regarding the co-creation of INHERIT technical or technological services, its progress and interim results from the 1st phase or co-creation of three are presented in **chapter 6**.

In total, INHERIT's technical co-creation process is divided into three phases. In the first phase, information and feedback about the INHERIT services and, how they best can be integrated into the CH buildings, was collected from pilots. In the second phase, the focus is on the co-design of user friendly environments and the user-flow diagrams. In the third and last phase, the services are supposed to be available already in a demo version, allowing stakeholders to test them and solution providers to refine accordingly based on the feedback received.

The handbook is completed with short chapters on conclusions, furthermore, references and the appendix.

² The overall participatory approach was presented first time publicly during a session at the occasion of the New European Bauhaus Festival 2024 and gained valuable feedback for the further calibration of the process.

2. Engagement and Co-Creation Strategy

The co-creation process comprises eight different use cases related to the eight pilots covering design, renovation, monitoring at building scale and analysis, forecast and resilience to climate change at a city or neighbourhood scale. In addition to these pre-defined focal topics, INHERIT gives space to locally or regionally relevant social aspects feedbacked by stakeholders during the project.

To do so, INHERIT invites all relevant stakeholders affecting and being affected by the restoration and renovation process of the eight INHERIT pilot projects. The transformation process will be carried out in accordance with a bundle of working principles focusing on participatory processes, a multi-level engagement and a transdisciplinary approach.

The overall strategy is built on the results from project-internal co-design activities implemented and a preliminary stakeholder mapping, which has helped to identify participants from QH on European, regional, and local level. In general, this results in a dynamic stakeholder pool as well as innovative formats of co-creation workshops and activities. The stakeholder pool consists of representatives from QH from a local and a transregional or European level, same time invites volunteers from civil society and volunteers from cultural management, research and technology to co-create and take advantage from INHERIT processes and results. Representatives from civil society (including citizens or community members) are an important target group to extract the social value and potential derived from the heritage building in the INHERIT social labs.

At the end of the project, at least **800 stakeholders** shall be identified and reached through **25 research and co-creation activities** comprising the INHERIT labs, the MSF, the S-LCA and further dissemination and exploitation activities.

Approximately 100 stakeholders linked to each INHERIT pilot shall be reached out to by consortium partners involving them in a research, co-creation, or dissemination activity. In any case, this a flexible scheme and will be adapted to the needs of each pilot.

Following the lab approach and best practice, INHERIT social labs work with the same group of participants throughout the entire lab process, leading to the establishment of a temporary partnership. In any case, the diverse settings and the local context of INHERIT social labs need more flexibility, and therefore, labs will engage a minimum of 10 participants in the lab activities but reach out and involve about 100 stakeholders each during the project. Furthermore, the MSF invites expert groups from a transregional and European level tackling INHERIT's focal topics for presentation events and workshops.

A set of internal steps in the starter phase of INHERIT helped to foster the framework for the engagement strategy and methodological approach extracting the site-specific conditions and needs of pilot projects. The following steps have been implemented, presented in a chronological order in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Overview on co-design steps during M1-M8

Course of Action	Method/s	Result/s
Kick-off workshop to build a joint vision of stakeholders and the labs (all partners) M2	Design thinking	Additional focus on the social layer of pilots included in the site-specific specific engagement strategies of pilots to build eight social labs
Initial stakeholder mapping (all pilot partners) M2 to M3	Desk research	Definition of sectors, groups, potential end user, engagement level: Basis of the use case description and initial engagement strategy
Preparatory context analysis and planning of lab establishment activities M2 to M3	Internal explorative interviews and brainstorming	Basis of the use case descriptions and tailor-made engagement strategies
Train-the-trainer workshop on co-creation and social labs M5	Capacity building session: lab approach, design, roles, methods on co-creation	Pilot leading consortium partners prepared for the establishment of lab in their local context
Train-the-trainer workshop follow-up session on social dimensions in in the pilot projects hand in hand with the train-the-trainer on the S-LCA M5	Workshop on ISO 26000 and vision statement building	Initial self-assessment on social responsibility dimensions in the pilot projects, building a vision statement for the co-creation process in INHERIT
Train-the-trainer on the S-LCA M5	Capacity building: S-LCA as a method for INHERIT	Introduction to the tool, reflection on the value for cultural heritage, preparation of the baseline assessment
Brainstorming on the NEB values in the context of pilots	Co-analysis workshop	Workshop with INHERIT consortium to transfer and principles to the INHERIT project
MSF kick-off with WP leading consortium partners M6	Co-design workshop	Rational, major objectives, structures, roles

MSF follow-up meeting with WP leading consortium partners M7	Co-design workshop	Initial agenda-setting of the MSF
Presentation at the NEB Festival 2024 with external stakeholders M7	Public discussion	Mutual learning with other European projects on best practice on NEB
INHERIT services: call with service providers with external stakeholders M8	Co-creation workshop	Alignment of 28 user stories with stakeholder needs

In INHERIT, CH is understood as a reservoir of creativity, well-being, identity, and knowledge that is useful to people and can inspire the participatory research process and the co-design of i.e. utilisation plans of CH buildings. This cultural value represented by historic buildings denotes local identity as well as communities and individuals and their important role in tackling societal or social problems in the INHERIT pilots.

Participatory research and co-creation settings in INHERIT intend to transfer this value into a **culture of engagement** within the project and in the work with external stakeholders. This approach is interlinked with different modes of collaboration. To give a concrete example, during the project kick-off meeting (M1) a design thinking session on relevant stakeholders joining the co-creation activities in INHERIT was implemented. Moreover, the rapid and creative session inspired INHERIT consortium partners to do an initial identification of most important stakeholder groups for each pilot case.

In parallel to the co-design efforts with consortium partners as presented in table 1, a review of literature and best practices was conducted to identify appropriate methodologies and interventions. Results from this review contribute to the use-case analysis of eight INHERIT pilots tackling opportunities for social inclusion and social innovation.

2.1. Literature Review and Best Practice

The initial literature review enabled a first definition of sectors, key stakeholder groups and potential roles of these stakeholders in the pilot sites and resulted in an assumptive mapping of their needs and expectations. It feeds into a literature pool (list) that is made available to consortium

partners, and later to the participants of the INHERIT MSF through a so-called Info Desk, which becomes part of the INHERIT website, where it provides main information and a Q&A related to the MSF (starting in M14). The list will be updated on a regular basis.

At the outset of the literature review, a search was conducted on Google Scholar, Web of Science and Scopus. Latest publications such as scientific articles and practice-related documents like project reports (deliverables) and policy briefs published between 2018-2024 were collected. When it comes to topics of these publications, they all deal with cultural heritage-related subjects, with some exceptions in cases where adjacent topics in publications with great relevance were found. The search parameters also encompassed the pilot countries (Croatia, France, Greece, Spain, Latvia, Poland, Sweden, Türkiye) focusing on publications in English. Keywords were identified during bilateral brainstorming sessions with the eight pilot lead partners beforehand.

Table 2: Keywords used in the literature and best practice search

Keywords	
Referring to the "must include" command: cultural heritage, inclusion, stakeholder engagement	beauty, climate resilience, co-creation, collaborative creativity, community-led innovation, cross-sector partnership, cultural tourism, cultural heritage management, decision-making, energy efficient building, governance, green technology, New European Bauhaus, multi-stakeholder collaboration, participatory design, retrofit, social innovation, social responsibility, sustainability, sustainable valorisation, togetherness, user-driven innovation

The initial search yielded over 10,000 publications and articles. Further refinement was carried out by using the "must include" command to focus the search on the terms "cultural heritage", "inclusion", "stakeholder engagement". This refined search yielded a result of 63 relevant references, instrumental for the operation and enhanced understanding of the social labs both as a research method and as a practical intervention. The results comprised also some lighthouse project related reports and policy briefs from European level.

Figure 2: Process and hits of the systematic literature search

The search resulted in a collection of relevant literature related to the six overarching focal points framing the work in INHERIT. These are:

- CH and social innovation
- CH and organisational governance
- CH and retrofit
- CH and green technologies
- NEB values in the context of CH
- Best practices for social innovation in CH management

Each of these six focal points is reflected in one or more activity lines of INHERIT. The following overview presents the highlights of the INHERIT literature review done to prepare a solid knowledge base for the co-creation process.

Literature was searched and further classified along a set of pre-defined keywords relating to the six focal points as mentioned. In total, >70 publications were selected as key literature, thus will serve the engagement, the co-creation, and the social innovation activities, furthermore, the social lab activities as methodological and theoretical backbone in the further course of implementation.

The field of **CH and social innovation (including engagement)** is rapidly growing, both as an academic research field and as a policy subject. This has also become evident in the literature review, where social innovation and cultural heritage tops the list of key references selected with <20 publications. In terms of most important reference points for our social lab (and MSF) activities, the following should be mentioned: European Commission on citizen engagement (2024) and about innovation in cultural heritage research (2018), the OECD on culture and creative industries enabling cross innovation (2018, 2020, 2021, 2022) on the policy-making, as well as Aureli & Del Baldo (2023) and Carayannis and Campell (2009, 2012, 2014), who write about the co-production of innovation, including social innovation, through transdisciplinary approaches and the involvement of multi-stakeholders from QH, on the academic side.

Social innovation and engagement is also reverberated in the context of NEB values, which promote diversity along accessibility and affordability as inseparable characteristics of a society in transformation (2022, 2023, 2024, 2024a) and embrace EU Green Deal issues such as climate change mitigation, energy efficiency or green technologies in the context of tangible cultural heritage (2023). With its particular focus on co-creation (as part of the social labs) and inclusive cultural heritage management (as part of the S-LCA), the **INHERIT project attains an important role in contributing** real-life insights, along with documentations, to the emerging (but still nascent) field of social innovation in cultural heritage (management).

According to the literature, participatory approaches that are based on the principles of trust, human agency and inclusion can create the right conditions for long-term commitment by all stakeholders involved – be it in landscape restoration (Gutierrez et al. 2023), biodiversity conservation (Lopez-Rodriguez et al. 2020) or energy efficiency improvement (Macia-Torregrosa et al. 2023), all of which are exemplary topics adjacent to cultural heritage. To enhance and refine its own participatory approaches, INHERIT again draws on the relevant literature compiled in its literature pool. Together, for the three focal points **cultural heritage and organisational governance, the NEB values in cultural heritage and the best practices for social innovation in cultural heritage management, >20 key literature examples were collected**. Key publications are Mahmoud et al (2021), Lopez-Rodriguez et al (2020) and Torchia et al (2023) on the academic, and European Commission (2022, 2021), European Parliament (2022) on the policy-making side. Similar to the two focal points earlier, **INHERIT puts into force a set of concrete activities to contribute to the advancement of these fields**. Apart from the S-LCA, which was already mentioned, INHERIT pro-actively works on diffusing and fostering the NEB values as guiding principles for the pilots work in the future.

As a direct consequence, the project seeks to establish its eight pilots as best practices on the landscape of socially innovative cultural heritages examples in the medium (during the project lifetime) and long-term (beyond the project lifetime) future.

Lastly, **the two focal points of retrofit and green technologies**, two technical aspects of cultural heritage, are **closely interlinked to INHERIT's work on co-creating the INHERIT solutions and user-scenarios**. In addition, they offer space for our activity line on social engagement and NEB values as guiding principles for the future work of project pilots – given the fact that technological features are promoted in NEB values as well, an important bridge-building between INHERIT solution development, NEB value capacity building and retrofit scenarios (as one of the result of the user scenarios developed) has been established in the context of the project. For these two focal points, <30 key literature examples were selected. As just mentioned, also these two focal points will **benefit from the work done in INHERIT**. With the technical experts gathered in the project consortium, who are brought together with experts on co-creation, stakeholder engagement and NEB value transfer to the built CH environment, INHERIT is in an ideal position to contribute innovative technological solutions, which are user-centred, socially inclusive, and energy-friendly at the same time, to the European cultural heritage sector.

In addition to the literature review, 25 best practice cases were filtered using pre-defined keywords. This list is frequently updated and serves as a knowledge and contact pool for the INHERIT MSF. The living document, which provides short project descriptions and additional keywords, is available in the INHERIT project online database. This selection serves as a knowledge hub for the INHERIT consortium and the pilot partners in particular. It includes projects at European, national, and regional levels and highlights lighthouse projects and innovative niche projects, equally. The following seven best practice examples show efforts related to sustainability, urban development, stakeholder engagement, and innovative initiatives across various contexts.

The establishment of the container garden, **I'Orto della SME (1)**, within the School of Management and Economics at the University of Turin is a prime example, emphasising its role as a self-managed hub fostering social cohesion around sustainability issues (Torchia et al. 2023). This project, part of the Proposal for Citizen Engagement framework and the NEB Initiative, demonstrates the effective application of NEB principles in addressing social inclusion, equality, and sustainable production and consumption.

Furthermore, the case of **Kiruna (2)**, Sweden, undergoing urban transformation due to mining impacts, prompts discussions about the sustainability of renovating historic 'Blackhorn' timber houses in a subarctic climate. This project aims to examine the challenges and opportunities in enhancing the energy efficiency of these buildings while preserving their heritage values (Luciani et al. 2019).

Examples such as the **Sierra de Guadarrama National Park (3)** in Spain and the **Gleis 21** project from Vienna illustrate how participatory approaches and NEB values drive transformative actions in urban

governance, landscape restoration, and health sector initiatives, promoting sustainability and social transformation (European Commission 2023, European Union 2024a, Lopez-Rodriguez et al. 2020, Macia-Torregrosa et al. 2023).

Research on multi-stakeholder engagement groups in energy transition processes and Urban Living Labs projects -- e.g. **CLEVER Cities**, **Sharing Cities** and **SUNEX (all 4)** – provides insights into collaborative governance mechanisms and co-creation pathways for sustainable urban development (Gutierrez et al. 2023, Mahmoud et al. 2021). Additionally, the analysis of governance arrangements within protected areas sheds light on stakeholder participation in conservation decision-making and emphasises the importance of inclusive mechanisms (Escario-Chust et al. 2023, Lopez-Rodriguez et al. 2020).

Lastly, innovative projects such as the comprehensive refurbishment of the **Lagos Park residential building (5)** in Madrid and initiatives like **Flytevi (6)** in Gothenburg or the **Hydoscope (7)** in Lisbon showcase practical approaches to enhancing energy efficiency, promoting sustainable communities, and utilising water resources for urban greening and community development (Macia-Torregrosa et al. 2023, European Union 2024). All examples underscore the significance of collaborative efforts, stakeholder engagement, and innovative solutions in advancing sustainability goals and fostering inclusive, resilient communities.

2.2. Collaborative Strategies in Research, Creation and Governance

This document outlines three phases of collaboration. While the first phase brings together the expertise of the consortium partners to co-design the stakeholder engagement strategy and the MSF, the second phase invites multi-stakeholders to take part in the INHERIT social labs and the MSF and to contribute with their knowledge. Co-design and co-creation strategies need to be also aligned with further activities integrating values and strategies of the NEB. The third phase focuses on practical steps of co-production and the implementation of interventions. This final phase aims to gain expert feedback from the MSF, which is a second mean for cross-disciplinary expert collaboration and participation.

2.2.1. Collaboration in the Context of CH Governance and Management

The MSF anticipates a form of temporary institutionalised collaboration and addresses innovative forms of partnership in governance and management of CH. The topic has gained interest in the CH related discourse i.e. mirrored by a set of principles indicated by the OECD. These principles can serve as the basis for developing innovative standards in governance and management for the cultural heritage sector including: (1) legitimacy and voice, (2) strategic direction, (3) performance, (4) responsibility, and (5) justice (Shipley & Kovacs 2008). Governance and the management of CH have evolved from being solely the responsibility of the state and public bodies to more collaborative approaches involving various actors (Žuvela et al. 2023) such as public-civil

partnerships, public-private-community partnerships or trends deriving from participatory approaches or a sustainable development synergy.

2.2.2. Modes of Collaboration

To operationalise the concepts of participation and co-creation in INHERIT, the following differentiation of collaboration modes is helpful: The terms co-creation, co-design and co-production are used to describe the development of initiatives involving one individual or multiple stakeholder(s).

Figure 3: INHERIT’s design of collaboration and definition of modes

Co-design, co-creation, and co-production are collaborative approaches that involve stakeholders in different stages of the development process and make the process and solutions more socially inclusive and responsive to the needs of those who will be affected by the outcomes. Co-design is the process where partners and/or stakeholders work together to define a problem and then develop or align methods for implementation. Co-creation goes a step further by involving all stakeholders in both defining the problem and implementing the solution. It’s an inclusive approach that combines the creative input from everyone.

Co-production is primarily about the implementation phase, it emphasises the active contribution of users in the creation of the service or solution. All three approaches have essential distinctions for cultural heritage, particularly related to the role of stakeholders and the extent and timing of their engagement. The following overview comprises three definitions (Vargas et al. 2022) which are further contextualised within the INHERIT project.

Table 3: Forms of collaborative design, creation, and production in INHERIT

Definition	Co-design	Co-creation	Co-production
	<p>Co-design describes the active collaboration between stakeholders in the design of solutions to a pre-specified problem. Results are framed by a set of objectives. Consultations and</p>	<p>Co-creation refers to the collaborative approach of creative problem-solving by multi-stakeholders at all stages of the project, from the problem identification and solution generation through to implementation and evaluation.</p>	<p>Co-production refers to implementing previously determined solutions or, services or lab projects with stakeholders agreed problem or question.</p>

	workshop settings are applicable.		
Implementation in INHERIT	Consortium partners contribute to the co-design of the processes and approaches applied in the stakeholder mapping like the stakeholder groups, the social labs and its setting and the MSF, which was co-designed during two internal workshops.	Multi-stakeholders are engaged in the co-creation of innovative solutions and services focusing on the social layer of each pilot. This can be e.g. the re-use concepts of buildings or working on the placemaking. In addition, end users feedback to technical solutions.	Consortium and multi-stakeholders are jointly planning and implementing their social lab activities and define together a lab project. This can include e.g. a prototype, a design object, a model construction, an exhibition, an educational event or a study visit etc.

2.2.3. Collaborative Design Thinking as Methodology

In the context of INHERIT, collaborative or participatory design thinking extends the basic concept by incorporating the idea of “intelligence of the many” into the design thinking process. Engaging end users and multi-stakeholders enhances the meaningfulness of innovation and promotes social acceptance and appropriation of results.

In general, design thinking is an impactful approach for quickly bringing together the expertise of multi-stakeholders to collaborate on solutions. As a collaborative methodology, design thinking is a framework that guides the entire problem-solving in an innovation process and emphasises the mindset on human-centred design principles.

In INHERIT, design thinking is defined as an iterative process used by consortium partners to understand end users and stakeholders, to challenge assumptions in their pilots, to redefine problems and objectives and to create innovative solutions for testing. The approach is also useful to tackle hardly defined problems and can involve different creative phases, such as empathise, define, ideate, prototype and test, which are connected in iterative feedback loops.

The methodology is applied to enable the collaboration between experts from the INHERIT consortium and end users or key stakeholders in the social labs and the MSF. In the initial phase of the project, all design thinking phases are included such as to empathise, define, ideate, prototype and test. Moreover, social labs and MSF integrate formalised and open approaches for iterative feedback.

Within the broader INHERIT methodological framework, the method of participatory design thinking aims to generate solutions to the research and co-creation process or to the INHERIT services and technology tools and includes practices like brainstorming, sketching, or prototyping as discrete tasks within the design thinking process. The approach sets the stage for a human-centric mindset, and at the same time provides concrete tools and exercises to apply that mindset to the co-design activities with consortium partners and the co-creation process with external stakeholders.

The method participatory design thinking was applied firstly during the INHERIT kick-off meeting to brainstorm and identify in small working groups stakeholder types with strong motivation to collaborate in the INHERIT social labs and the MSF. In a later step, participatory design thinking was applied with the help of Mentimeter surveys to build a robust and appropriate concept for the MSF jointly with WP lead partners from the INHERIT consortium.

The following figure shows sketches drawn by pilot partners at the first participatory design thinking session during the project's kick-off meeting. in the task was to identify the "ideal or perfect" stakeholder for each pilot building. The example shows the creative output of the first design thinking session, which was also an appropriate ice breaker to build interdisciplinary INHERIT teams quickly.

Metz, France - BOUYGUES

Izmir, Türkiye - IBB

Visby, Sweden - UU

Jastrebarsko, Croatia - REGEA

Riga, Latvia - RPR

Athens, Greece - ELLET

Gdynia, Poland - FASADA

Castile and León, Spain - CARTIF

Figure 4: Creative results from design thinking session during the project kick-off meeting

2.3. Identification of Key Stakeholders and End Users

The INHERIT stakeholder mapping also follows an iterative process. After an initial phase based on desk research and the analysis of partners network, pilot leaders identify together with lab participants stakeholders with a stake in the INHERIT process and results, key knowledge holders, decision takers and influencers and potential end users of the INHERIT solutions.

Table 4: Phases of the INHERIT stakeholder mapping

Phases and Sequences	Months	Activities	(Expected) Outcomes
Stakeholder groups brainstorming workshop	M2	The pilot partners collaborated to propose various stakeholder groups that are essential to our project. This workshop facilitated a collective effort to identify key stakeholders, leveraging the diverse perspectives and expertise of the pilot partners.	Creation of a comprehensive list of stakeholder groups. This list would then serve as the foundational basis for the detailed stakeholder mapping process in the next phase.
Identification of stakeholders	M2 – M3	Identifying specific individuals or entities within each stakeholder group, gathering detailed information about their roles, interests, and influence on the project, and ensuring that all relevant stakeholders are recognised and documented.	List of identified stakeholders with detailed profiles for each, and a clear understanding of their potential impact and engagement in the project.
Continuous refinement of stakeholder mapping	M4 – M39	Regularly updating the stakeholder list to reflect changes in stakeholder roles, interests, or influence, and continuously assessing and adjusting engagement strategies based on ongoing feedback.	Up-to-date and dynamic stakeholder map that accurately reflects current stakeholder roles, interests, and influence, and a set of adaptive engagement strategies that address the evolving needs and concerns of stakeholders.

Giving stakeholders a clear role and influence in the co-creation processes guarantees alignment between the project's objectives and the needs and expectations of the end users and other relevant parties. This involvement fosters a collaborative environment, where all stakeholders have a voice in shaping the project's direction and outcomes including vulnerable groups and minorities. QH stakeholders for INHERIT project represent a group of stakeholders in one place with function of reflecting social needs. Highlighted stakeholder groups from QH are further aligned with INHERIT for the stakeholder mapping. They are expected to include several perspectives while contributing to the co-creation in the INHERIT social labs and the collaborative reflection and mutual learning in the MSF. By actively involving stakeholders throughout the mapping process, the project can address diverse perspectives, anticipate potential challenges, and deliver more sustainable

solutions. To better understand the specific role of stakeholders in the co-creation process, the INHERIT mapping developed the following definitions:

Stakeholder	People (or an organisation or community) with an interest or concern and influence related to the project and its objectives. Stakeholders representing QH groups can be relevant for the INHERIT social labs and the MSF.
End User	Person (or an organisation or community), who uses findings and results of the project. End users are relevant for the INHERIT social labs and the MSF. In the context of technical and technology solutions, end users contribute to the social labs used as testbeds with their feedback regarding design and usability.

To achieve the best results in the stakeholder mapping, pilot lead partners reflected the following questions:

- Who will be affected by the project? Who can influence results?
- Who can take advantage of results of INHERIT?
- Whose voices might not be heard? (support to the socially inclusive strategy of INHERIT)
- Who will be responsible to manage results? (facilitators, municipality representatives, NGOs, companies etc.)

To further differentiate the engagement with stakeholders, the **engagement intensity is categorised into five distinct levels**, each representing a varying degree of interaction and involvement. These levels are information, consultation, involvement, collaboration, and end user. These engagement levels are aligned with numerical values 1 to 5 as provided in the engagement level column of the INHERIT's stakeholder database template.

Figure 5: Levels of stakeholder engagement in the INHERIT social labs

Information	<p>This stakeholder group is identified to be at the minimum level of engagement. Communication is mostly one-way, stakeholder input is not actively sought; however, transparency and awareness are important. Stakeholders at the informing level show low to moderate interest and have a low level of influence, with limited or no direct influence on the decision-making process.</p>
Consultation	<p>Stakeholder's feedback, opinions, and suggestions is actively obtained. It goes beyond simply informing stakeholders and provides an opportunity for them to express their views. Stakeholders are asked for their input, and their perspectives are considered in the decision-making process. These stakeholders present a moderate to high interest in our project, however, a low to moderate influence.</p>
Involvement	<p>Stakeholders take engagement a step further by actively involving them in the decision-making process. These stakeholders have a high level of interest and a moderate to high level of influence on our project. Therefore, they are seen as partners rather than mere recipients of information and are given the opportunity to provide input and influence the outcome. In this level of stakeholder engagement, stakeholders have valuable knowledge, experiences, and perspectives that can significantly enhance the project's outcomes.</p>
Collaboration	<p>The collaboration process involves stakeholders with high levels of interest, commitment, and influence in our project. At this stage, stakeholders are active partners in decision-making and their input is given equal weight alongside other factors. That means they can participate in shaping the project or decision and share a sense of ownership - so we must treat them as part of our team.</p>
End User	<p>The last level of engagement level, the end users are the affected category of people on whom the results of the project will apply directly. End users might be persons that have not contributed or collaborated in the project yet but are the end user of the project output.</p>

The mapping along engagement level supports the establishment of multi-stakeholder groups within the eight INHERIT pilots and gives a platform to a community of interest for cross-pilot knowledge sharing and new partnerships among institutions and stakeholders across the project. By actively involving stakeholders throughout the mapping process, the project can better address diverse perspectives, anticipate potential challenges, and ultimately deliver more impactful and sustainable solutions. The stakeholder involvement in INHERIT is characterised by ongoing, voluntary participation, fostering transparent and dynamic dialogues across diverse stakeholder cohorts.

Given the distinct nature of the pilots, stakeholder involvement is based on the QH concept and encompasses seven pre-defined sectors and organisation as public sector, private sector, higher education, and research, the third sector and furthermore, media, the cultural and creative industries (CCI) construction sector and from one open (other) category.

Figure 6: QH model and major sectors for INHERIT

The main sectors can be further specified in stakeholder groups and its organisational form such as civil society organisations (CSOs), non-governmental organisations (NGOs), municipality representatives, policymakers, academic researchers, cultural and creative professionals, social innovators or entrepreneurs, and representatives of the local communities, taking care of vulnerable and underrepresented minorities.

A first analysis reveals the following results: Across the pilots, the public sector emerges as a prominent category with a substantial number of representatives important to each pilot. This suggests a strong commitment from governmental or public institutions towards promoting sustainable and inclusive living environments. While the private sector's participation varies across pilots, its involvement remains crucial for driving innovation and implementing sustainable solutions. However, the relatively low representation in some pilots in this preliminary analysis indicates potential challenges in engaging private sector stakeholders and underscores the need for further outreach and promotion.

Looking at the higher education and research sector makes significant participation in several pilots, contributing expertise and knowledge to address complex challenges visible. Their involvement highlights the importance of research-driven approaches in shaping sustainable and inclusive living environments. Certain pilots involve stakeholders from industry-specific sectors such as construction, indicating targeted efforts to address sector-specific challenges and opportunities. This focused engagement allows for the integration of sustainable practices and technologies within these industries, driving positive change at a sectoral level.

While each pilot focuses on a specific mix of sectors, there are opportunities for cross-sector collaboration to leverage diverse expertise and resources. Collaboration between the public and private sectors, academia, and other stakeholders can lead to the development of holistic solutions that address multifaceted challenges and maximise impact. While all pilots follow a diverse stakeholder engagement strategy, there are areas for further exploration and expansion. These include increasing private sector participation, the enhancing of collaboration between sectors, and the representation from sectors such as general education, media and the third sector.

Additionally, ongoing efforts to engage stakeholders and foster partnerships will be crucial in driving the project's success and creating lasting impacts on sustainable and inclusive living environments. Further analysis of core stakeholders and potential end users is presented in the use case analyses and the first versions of the engagement strategies.

Furthermore, a list of European organisations with relevance to INHERIT can be found in this handbook (appendix) that supplements the stakeholder mapping related to the eight pilots and their local or national focus. INHERIT will reach out to these organisations mainly by the means of the MSF.

2.4. Introducing ISO 26000 on Social Responsibility to INHERIT Pilots

Pilot lead partners were asked to conduct a self-assessment with the help of ISO 26000 standard during the stakeholder mapping and lab preparation phase. The initial results offer insights into the diverse perspectives on social responsibility priorities.

ISO 26000 is not intended to be certified but shall be used as a practical framework of critical success factors referring to the social layer. In this context, social responsibility can be defined as the responsibility of an organisation for the impacts of its decisions and activities on the society and the environment, through transparent, ethical, and socially engaged behaviour that contributes to sustainable development. A socially responsible approach includes the expectations of stakeholders, is practiced in all its relationships, and can be implemented in an organisation or project. The applied standard includes seven core subjects, which are:

- **Community involvement:** All organisations have an impact on the communities, where they operate, and their active participation can help ensure the well-being of these communities. ISO 26000 offers guidance e.g. on the active community involvement, the support for civil institutions, the promotion of education and culture, job creation and skills development, technology development and access and social investments.
- **Environment:** ISO standard urges organisations to minimise their environmental impacts and ensure sustainable resource consumption. Among other issues, organisations shall implement initiatives to prevent pollution, to use resources sustainably, to mitigate and adapt to climate change, to protect the environment, biodiversity, and take care of the restoration of natural habitats.
- **Fair operations:** ISO standard calls for organisations to deal ethically with customers, partners, suppliers, contractors, competitors, and government agencies to bring about positive results. Fair operating practices include, preventing corruption, responsible political involvement, fair competition, promoting social responsibility in the value chain and respecting property rights.
- **Human rights:** ISO standard provides guidance for organisations e.g. to support human rights, particularly by allowing free organisation and collective negotiation, providing equal employment opportunities, preventing all forms of discrimination, and resolving grievances.
- **Labor practices:** Responsible practices address i.e. employment and contractual relationships, working conditions and social protection, social dialogue, Health and safety at work and human development and training in the workplace.
- **Organisational governance:** ISO standard encourages organisations e.g. to consider accountability, transparency, and ethics in their decision-making process and governing practices. In some cases, participatory approaches can be productive.
- **User issues:** ISO standard raises awareness to promote fair and sustainable economic and social development. A responsible approach to consumer issues includes e.g. fair marketing practices, protection of health and safety, sustainable consumption strategies, user education, dispute resolution, data and privacy protection, fair use and ensuring essential products and services are available to everyone, including vulnerable or disadvantaged groups.

In the context of the eight INHERIT pilot projects, the environment emerges as the top concern, universally recognised for its critical importance in fostering sustainability. This ISO 26000 core subject was followed in the rankings by community involvement and organisational governance indicating a shared understanding of the significance of community engagement and effective internal management structures. However, there is notable variability in the importance attributed to fair operating practices, human rights, labour practices, and user issues. While some pilots emphasise these aspects as important, others consider them less important or not important, underscoring differing priorities and perspectives among stakeholders. This diversity of rankings

underscores the complexity of navigating these priorities and highlights the need for nuanced approaches to address the multi-faceted social, environmental, and ethical challenges facing organisations today in general and in the INHERIT pilots in particular.

MOST IMPORTANT	The environment is consistently rated as the most important aspect across multiple pilots, reflecting a shared emphasis on environmental sustainability.
SECOND TIER IMPORTANCE	Community involvement and development as well as organisational governance are also frequently rated as important, suggesting recognition of the significance of community engagement and effective internal management structures.
VARIABLE IMPORTANCE	Fair operating practices, human rights, labour practices, and user issues receive mixed ratings across pilots, indicating differing perspectives on their significance in the realm of corporate responsibility.
LESS IMPORTANT	Labor practices and user issues are consistently rated as less important or not important across several pilots suggesting potential areas of disagreement or differing priorities among stakeholders.

The following figure gives an overview on the results of the self-assessment done by the eight pilot lead partners. Dealing with ISO 26000 as a framework enabled a first draft of a vision statement for each pilot as well as the anticipation of potential challenges when engaging stakeholders. Statements were designed on the basis of a self-assessment exercise regarding relevant social responsibility dimensions by partners and then further discussed in brainstorming meetings between WP leaders and pilot leaders. All statements are highlighted in the follow-up chapter.

Figure 7: Results of the pilot's self-assessment in the context of ISO 26000 core subjects

2.5. NEB Values as a Framework for Change

The NEB initiative by the EC connects the European Green Deal to daily lives and bridges between the world of science and technology, art, and culture. Transformation shall succeed along three inseparable values:

- sustainability, from climate goals to circularity, zero pollution, and biodiversity,
- aesthetics (or beauty), quality of experience and style beyond functionality,
- inclusion, from valuing diversity to securing accessibility and affordability.

Pilot partners have been diligently aligning the specific needs of their respective pilot projects with the overarching aspirations encapsulated by the NEB framework. This concerted effort serves as a foundational step towards catalysing a comprehensive and holistic transformation. A notable example of this alignment can be observed in the pilot cases that embody the core principles of NEB, including inclusion, aesthetics, and sustainability. Within these case studies, these values are not merely abstract concepts but guiding beacons illuminating the path towards sustainable and socially impactful design solutions. In particular, the pilot cases place a deliberate emphasis on inclusion and aesthetics, recognising their pivotal roles in driving the initial stages and shaping the overarching vision. Moreover, the interdisciplinary nature of the pilot cases underscores the NEB's call for a convergence of diverse perspectives and expertise. By integrating various inputs, needs, and visions into the project's fabric, the pilot project can harness the collective wisdom and creativity of stakeholders from different domains. This interdisciplinary approach not only enriches the design process but also ensures that the resulting solutions are robust, innovative, and capable of addressing multifaceted challenges.

During the first months of the INHERIT project has been fostering the understanding of the NEB' values and working principles among the consortium partners. This has been done by the means of targeted online meetings, in which the pilots' needs have been tailored. This is mainly related to the outcomes of a workshop conducted in WP6. During the workshop all eight pilots identified the ambitions within NEB values and working principles. The mapped information builds a foundation to start working with the NEB over time as a holistic framework for change.

Furthermore, for planning activities the following resources have been used: NEB Compass, NEB Toolbox, NEB Dashboard, information on NEB Prices 2021, 2022, 2022, 2023, 2024 and other case studies from the NEB Community.

Targeted online meetings with the pilots were conducted, in which the goal was to learn the latter's necessities and ambitions to help them making the most of INHERIT by using the NEB approach. The pilots were encouraged to give feedback on their expectations of the project and on the skills that they would like to achieve. For this, a series of online activities was carried out such as Mentimeter polls and Miro Board presentations, with which the pilots were able to share their comments and

ideas on the development of the project, inspired by the NEB. This was conducted in synergy with other tasks in WP2 and with the WP6 (capacity building, policy support, and standardisation). The integration across work packages is mainly due to the fact that the NEB initiative is understood as a framework for affirmative action and change, including constant learning, refinement of skills, and thus part of the capacity building programme, dissemination, and innovative approach to resource efficiency.

In this way ICLEI also learned the deficiencies of the pilots and the skills that need to be reinforced. Based on this background, ICLEI is now designing a strategy that will aim to tackle those, while helping the pilots to embed the tools and services necessary to accomplish the projects' objectives. In this aspect, the feedback received from the polls and presentations on the expectations of the project is helping ICLEI to guide the development of INHERIT in a way that aligns with the values and working principles of the NEB.

Furthermore, the pilots have regularly been updated with NEB related opportunities that could synergise the pilots' local stories, as well as recognised and hidden CH assets with the NEB movement. In relation to this, the pilots were offered the opportunity to engage with the representatives of other NEB projects (e.g. NEBStar, CultuurCampus - NEB Lighthouse Project, HeriACT) in a way they could learn from similar projects that were carried out and discussed during the NEB Festival 2024.

Furthermore, the examples presented by ICLEI were thought to specifically target pilots' profile and needs. As an example of this, the Polish and French pilots were presented with a project from the NEB Prizes 2021 edition, from which they could learn about the renovation of a historical residence in the Normandy region of France.

Additionally, ICLEI got in contact with INHERIT's sister projects CALECHE, SINCERE and Herit4ages, and engaged them in an active collaboration between the projects with the goal of sharing developed skills and rich experiences from which to learn.

To a greater extent, ICLEI engaged a representative from CALECHE project to act as a speaker for the INHERIT led webinar on 11th April 2024, which was an official satellite event of the New European Bauhaus Festival 2024.

Finally, in synergy with other INHERIT tasks working on technical aspects and feedback loops for the adoption of the INHERIT solutions, and beyond the local experiences, needs and visions are gathered by iterative cycles of collection, refinement, and assessment of the stakeholders' inputs. They build the basis for main outcomes of this task - two NEB online meetings on values and working principles. Overall, the methodology for this task includes the following steps:

Table 5: Methodological steps to transfer NEB values

Phase	Months	Activities	Expected outcomes
Mapping	M3 - M4	Mapping needs, sharing understanding of the NEB based on the preliminary identification of NEB ambitions as signalled by the eight pilots	NEB flowers for each pilots reflecting the NEB ambitions at the initial stage of the project (based on the approach proposed in the NEB Toolbox)
Iteration 1	M5	Identifying possible synergies and learning inputs from the NEB community	Getting to know the NEB framework, good overview of examples and case studies
Planning And Immersion 1 In the NEB Ecosystem	M6 - M7	Designing INHERIT webinar as part of the NEB Festival 2024 “Co-creating next generation solutions for heritage buildings”, including interventions from the NEBStar, CULTUURCAMPUS and HeriACT projects, with active participation of the INHERIT pilots in designing own visions as a “destination” that could be reached with the NEB	Establishing cooperation with projects from the NEB Community, sharing INHERIT examples with the broader audience during the NEB Festival 2024 (satellite event)
Planning And Co-Design of Workshops	M8 - M11	Planning meetings with the pilots and iterative mapping of NEB related needs to frame the workshops to be conducted in this task	Defining the target audience, inviting relevant stakeholders, designing the flow of events
Immersion 2 In the NEB Ecosystem	M12	1 st NEB INHERIT workshop on values targeting pilots and mainly local stakeholders, from the field of design, culture, built environment sector, policy	One online workshop connecting INHERIT pilots with the NEB framework
	M13	2 nd NEB INHERIT workshop on working principles targeting pilots and local stakeholders, mainly from the field of design, culture-built environment sector	One online workshop connecting INHERIT pilots with the NEB framework
Iteration 2	M14	Revision of NEB ambitions	Integration of the NEB approach in the capacity building programme and other activities across the WPs

2.6. Engagement Strategy in the INHERIT Pilot Activities

The stakeholder engagement strategy is based on three sequential stages, involving the stakeholder **identification**, the **analysis**, and the **engagement** through an iterative approach. The overall INHERIT **stakeholder engagement approach** and its single steps are presented in the following figure.

Figure 8: Stakeholder mapping and engagement strategy

During the internal co-design of process and approaches including a series of bilateral brainstorming exercises, group workshops and explorative interviews. The pilot lead partners highlighted the need of further clarification of technical advancements, policy and regulations, and financial support in the context of the ISO 26000 and the NEB. In general, all local partners in the pilot area sites were convinced that both were appropriate frameworks in fostering energy efficiency. In addition to the existing information on the buildings, sites, and pilot-related objectives, a further analysis enabled the creation of a tailor-made stakeholder engagement strategy for each pilot. This strategy describes

- complementary **issues of interest** with a focus on the social layer,
- the **site-specific context** putting attention to the cultural, historic and geographic specifics,
- a **vision** statement with a focus on the social layer,
- an initial analysis of **core stakeholders** of the pilot,
- **anticipated challenges** and **concerns**, furthermore,
- initially identified opportunities to address **social inclusiveness** and **diversity** and
- a first analysis of how **NEB values** and principles can be transferred to the pilots.

Table 6: Stakeholders per pilot according INHERIT sectors identified in the initial mapping activity

STH Group \ Pilot	Pilot								
	Athens ELLET	Gdynia FASADA	Izmir IBB	Jastrebarsko REGEA	Metz BOUYGUES	Riga RPR	Valladolid CARTIF	Visby UU	
Public Sector	4	3	7	20	6	9	2	4	
Identified End User	-	-	1	6	-	7	2	3	

Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements

Private Sector	-	3	1	1	7	4	1	1
Identified End User	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	-
Higher Education & Research	1	-	3	1	-	1	-	1
Identified End User	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
General Education	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Identified End User	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Media	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Identified End User	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Construction Sector	2	-	1	-	3	-	-	1
Identified End User	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3rd Sector	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
Identified End User	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other	5	1	1	-	4	-	-	4
Identified End User	1	-	1	-	4	-	-	1
Total Number	13	7	13	22	21	14	3	11

In total, there were 104 stakeholders mapped reaching 3 to 22 stakeholders per pilot; from this group 30 end users were identified benefitting directly from the INHERIT solutions and potentially taking part in the INHERIT social labs. These numbers are interim, further collaborating stakeholders with at least an engagement level 3 to 4 are expected to be identified via snowballing research.

Through the iterative nature of the stakeholder mapping, the establishment of the social labs and its activities are at start will give the possibility to further refine and align the interim results.

In general, the majority of pilot cases are in need of broadening their stakeholder base to include representatives from all pillars of the quadruple helix model, encompassing research and education,

industry, policymaking, and civil society. This expansion of stakeholders is essential to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive approach to innovation, drawing upon diverse perspectives and expertise. Furthermore, the preliminary mapping of stakeholders must be extended to incorporate representation from the third sector, which includes non-profit organisations and community groups as well as from the cultural and creative industries recognising the valuable contributions and unique insights these sectors can offer. One of the primary challenges in this endeavor is the mobilisation of stakeholders with varying disciplinary backgrounds, fostering an environment where they can actively engage and share their experiences and knowledge. Cross-fertilisation workshops that facilitate dialogue and collaboration among consortium partners and stakeholders from different sectors will play a pivotal role in achieving this, promoting the exchange of ideas and best practices to enrich the collective learning experience across the diverse pilot cases.

Every pilot developed a vision statement through a collaborative design thinking session. An initial version can be found in the pilot use case engagement strategies. This version will be discussed in the INHERIT social labs and further developed together with the lab participants making it a jointly agreed vision statement for the pilot. In parallel, an overall vision statement for the co-creation process and social labs was created as directive testimonial:

CH is dynamic, for all and a container for multiple values: against this background, INHERIT's innovative practices and technologies shall contribute to creative climate leadership and new strategies for the sensitive valorisation of CH. Furthermore, CH management shall be improved by the reflection of social responsibility and the NEB values.

The following figure 8 shows the different European regions, where the eight INHERIT pilots are located mostly in an urban area. Further information on the location is presented in the following use case descriptions together with an initial strategy to set-up a multi-stakeholder group in each pilot. This group brings together all relevant stakeholders having a stake in the project outcomes, solutions, and services. The aim of the mapping is to bundle different interests at stakes and perspectives to frame problems with a "real-world" context and to design solutions through a collaborative manner. Initial strategies will be examined after the kick-off lab events and if necessary, aligned with the stakeholder feedback.

Figure 9: INHERIT pilot's geographical map

2.6.1. Athens – Greece | ELLETT

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
ELLETT building in Tripodon street, Athens, Greece	- 3,154,591	1 building, 2 floors, 503 m ² , built in the early 19 th century Originally used as a residence, now Ground floor: utilised for seminars and conferences 1 st floor: office of ELLETT headquarters
Objective/S (Based On GA)	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance energy performance in historical buildings facing challenges - Innovate solutions within facade modification restrictions - Address water infiltration damage and reduce heat losses from the roof - Control rising humidity and dampness in the designated area
Issues Of Interest (Results From Bilateral Brainstorming)	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasise social responsibility and sustainability - Enhance living conditions and accessibility - Improve sewer systems and combat stone deterioration - Upgrade inadequate infrastructure due to over-tourism

Site-Specific Context

ELLET's building, situated on Tripodon street beneath the Acropolis, holds historical significance dating back to ancient Greek times. Once the hub of political and cultural activity, Tripodon street housed key public buildings like the Agora. Constructed in the early 19th century, ELLET's two-story building hosts seminars, conferences, and events on the ground floor, featuring cultural artifacts. The second floor accommodates ELLET's headquarters offices. The building is in a dense metropolitan area.

Vision

ELLET is dedicated to upholding principles of social responsibility, sustainability, and exemplary stewardship of cultural heritage. As a cornerstone in Plaka, ELLET is committed to fulfil their social vision by preserving Greece's cultural heritage. Guided by this vision, the organisation pursues innovative practices that serve as a blueprint for sustainable development and guarantee a bright and resilient future for the following generations. ELLET optimises cultural heritage buildings in Greece by enhancing energy efficiency, preserving architectural identity, and integrating technology. Through innovative solutions, the pilot building showcases sustainable management practices. Key outcomes include identifying renovation plans that align with aesthetics, implementing smart features, and developing maintenance strategies.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

Transformative initiatives encounter expected hurdles, particularly in reconciling preservation and sustainability efforts. Essential sustainable practices encompass energy efficiency, renewable sources, waste reduction, eco-friendly materials, adaptive reuse, environmental education, flexible workspace design, community engagement, and employee participation. Yet, stringent regulations in Greece, notably in Plaka near the Acropolis, and bureaucratic procedures might result in approval delays. Moreover, end users' lack of familiarity with technology may present comprehension obstacles.

Stakeholders and End Users

A variety of stakeholders, such as journalists, engineers, students, local authorities, heritage preservation organisations, energy committees, resident initiatives, and professional associations, are actively involved in ELLET's initiatives. These stakeholders bring expertise and resources to promote environmental awareness, heritage preservation, and sustainable development in Athens. End users include attendees of the "Panorama of Ecological Films" festival and contributors to ELLET's special councils. In the initial mapping there were 13 stakeholders and one end user identified.

Table 7: Initial mapping for the pilot in Athens by the consortium partner ELLET

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Athens	1	2	1	1	1	---	1	1	4	1
Level	1	2	3	4	5	---	1	1	1 2	4

Social Inclusion and Diversity

Promoting social inclusion fosters an environment where everyone can thrive, breaking barriers and celebrating diversity. Embracing various forms of diversity enriches the understanding and propels us towards a more equitable world. In historic areas like Plaka, it is crucial to include vulnerable or marginalised groups in co-creation processes. This includes people with disabilities, the elderly, long-time residents, and economically disadvantaged, ensuring their perspectives and needs are represented and addressed.

NEB Values

Mapping of the NEB values and working principles was conducted during collective meeting and in line with the recommendations included in the NEB toolbox. In general, the local partner in Athens attaches great importance to all three NEB values in the realisation of its project. The driving values are related to inclusion and beauty being more important at the initial stage of the project than inclusion. Furthermore, the pilot in Athens is targeting beyond-disciplinary approach, integrating various inputs, needs, and visions for the building in the context of energy efficiency. During later discussion on the NEB as a framework of the project (IV 2024), the local partners highlighted the need to consider many factors like regulations, social impact and land use policy.

Figure 10: ELLET's NEB values

2.6.2. Gdynia – Poland | FASADA

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
Social Residential Building in City of Gdynia, Poland	243,918	1 building, 3 floors, 1,168 m ² , built in 1928 Always in use as residential building
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimise renovation through INHERIT approach - Use advanced tech like H-BIM, Digital Twin (DT), AR/VR - Explore renewable energy in heritage buildings - Harmonise technologies for integrated plan 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prioritise resident wellbeing - Develop bicycle-friendly infrastructure - Resolve design disagreements between municipality and cultural heritage conservators to achieve social harmony 	

Site-specific Context

Gdynia, located on Poland's Baltic Sea coast, is ranking as the country's 12th-largest city. Noteworthy achievements include joining the UNESCO Creative Cities Network in 2021 and being designated a UNESCO City of Film, renowned for hosting the annual Gdynia Film Festival. Recognised for its exceptional quality of life, Gdynia was voted Poland's best city to live in by readers of The News in 2013. Despite its cultural heritage status, the ongoing renovation of the city-owned social residential

building, constructed in 1928, aims to preserve its original design while focusing on improving heating insulation. Importantly, residents will continue to reside in the building during the renovation, minimising disruptions to their daily lives.

Vision

The vision entails an innovative design proposal to the municipality, aligning with cultural heritage guidelines, and aiming to preserve the building's historical significance while meeting community needs. Emphasising a harmonious blend of tradition and modernity, the renovated structure is envisioned as a vibrant, sustainable asset for the municipality. Prioritising accessibility for individuals with disabilities ensures inclusion and enables full participation in community life, contributing to a revitalised and connected environment. FASADA implies renovation measures for residential buildings that prioritise design, maintenance planning, and energy efficiency while enhancing accessibility for occupants with disabilities. Their pilot project focuses on a social housing building, serving as a model for future developments. This approach aligns with the need of promoting sustainable, resource-efficient, and resilient cultural heritage assets.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

Anticipated challenges stem from diverse perspectives within the building community, with potential divisions between those open to collaboration and those expressing apprehension, particularly regarding rent increases. Navigating this divide presents a challenge in fostering a unified vision that addresses varying needs and concerns. Achieving a balance between community engagement, financial considerations, and inclusion will be crucial to overcoming these challenges and fostering a harmonious renovation process that genuinely reflects collective well-being.

Stakeholders and End Users

The stakeholders involved in the project include the Social Buildings Management (ZBILK), the Energy Department of the City of Gdynia, architecture students, tenants of demonstration buildings, neighbours of demo buildings, and experts specialising in building adjustments to accommodate people with disabilities. The tenants, as end users, benefit from the construction of the housing building by gaining access to more secure and comfortable living spaces. This improvement directly addresses housing needs within the community offering tangible benefits. There were seven stakeholders and no end users identified.

Table 8: Initial mapping for the pilot in Gdynia by the consortium partner FASADA

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Gdynia	---	3	---	---	1	---	---	---	1	2
Level	---	4	---	---	1	---	---	---	4	---

Social Inclusion and Diversity

After considering the social dimension and inclusion, the vision addresses the concerns of both cooperative residents and those apprehensive about potential rent increases, emphasising transparent communication and collaboration with the municipality. This inclusive approach aims to gather information and consider the diverse needs of families, individuals, and children ensuring the renovation plan caters to the well-being and preferences of all residents within the building.

NEB Values

The mapping of relevant NEB values and working principles was conducted during an online meeting and facilitated on the MIRO board. FASADA's priorities in the project are sustainability and togetherness with less focus on beauty at the initial stage. Also, participatory processes and multi-level engagement are targeted at the basic level to build first a robust foundation for future transformations. The local partner is however interested in fostering interdisciplinary approach to integrated various needs and visions throughout the project. During a later meeting in M7 more importance was associated with inclusivity and multi-level engagement, reflecting the internal processes and priorities.

Figure 11: FASADA's NEB values

2.6.3. Izmir – Türkiye | IBB

Pilot Case	City Population	Type Of Building
Ahmet Piriştina Izmir City Archive and Museum, City of Izmir, Türkiye	2,965,900	2 buildings, 2 floors, 2,921.5 m ² , build in 1932 Originally a fire station, now used as city archive, museum, and book café
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assess energy strategies - Improve indoor conditions - Facilitate historical renovation - Explore renewable energy options 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mitigate noise pollution from nearby main road and large windows - Resolve limited space issue in the library for better user accommodation - Implement comprehensive digitalisation strategy for preserving and accessing old newspapers 	

Site-specific Context

Izmir, a metropolitan city in Türkiye, is renowned for its strategic location along the Gulf of Izmir and the Gediz River Delta. The city's port, a vital hub for exports, features a free zone established through a Turkish-U.S. joint venture in 1990. Izmir is notable for its nine historic synagogues from 19th century, reflecting its cultural diversity. The city also hosts esteemed higher-education institutions

recognised nationwide. The pilot building, originally constructed as İzmir's first fire station after the 1922 İzmir Fire, holds significant historical value and serves multiple functions, including a museum exhibition area and offices.

Vision

The overarching vision centres on fostering social inclusion for all future users while establishing a sustainable utilisation model for the building: IBB is committed to implement sustainable and energy-efficient solutions for APIKAM and a multi-functional structure accommodating various users. The pilot case modernises and renovates the APIKAM building while preserving its historical significance and enhancing its functionality to meet contemporary needs. This includes revitalising the structure and improving the archive's efficiency and capacity to accommodate a wider range of valuable objects, reflecting a commitment to both preservation and adaptation to evolving demands.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

The project's feasibility requires addressing seismic challenges, such as earthquakes, and establishing collaborations with stakeholders to ensure its success. Furthermore, clear alignment and synergies between the INHERIT project and the municipality are essential to maximise mutual benefits and contribute to overall success, highlighting the need for a comprehensive and coordinated approach to project planning.

Stakeholders and End Users

The project involves various stakeholders, ranging from public sector entities like the İzmir First Conservation Council of Cultural Heritage to civil society organisations such as the İzmir National Library Foundation. Private sector representatives and constructors, as well as higher education and research institutions like Yaşar University and the İzmir Institute of Technology, are also engaged. Additionally, community members, including academic scholars and seminar participants/exhibition visitors, are involved, along with public authorities like the Department of City Planning Supervision. The implementation of the project aims to provide enhanced conditions in the Archive building for academic scholars, enabling in-depth research and study, while offering seminar participants and exhibition visitors increased opportunities for engagement with historical and cultural materials through dynamic and interactive discussions. In the initial mapping there were 13 stakeholders and four end users identified.

Table 9: Initial mapping for the pilot in Izmir by the consortium partner IBB

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Izmir	2	---	2	2	3	---	---	---	2	2
Level	4	---	1	5	1 5	---	---	---	4	4 5

Social Inclusion and Diversity

In efforts to improve accessibility, the pilot building offers toilets tailored for disabled individuals on the first floor, although the exhibit hall currently lacks accessibility; existing features include accessibility to the café, courtyard, and a designated parking space, with ongoing assessments to explore further measures for accommodating diverse needs, emphasising inclusion.

NEB Values

The mapping of relevant NEB values and working principles was conducted during a joint activity on a MIRO board. In realising its vision, IBB focuses on sustainability and togetherness by making the building accessible to everyone. Having in mind the historic importance of the building for the community, also the aspect of beauty is highly underlined and important for the transition. The local partner sees a lot of potential in transdisciplinary approach, trying to go beyond disciplines during the project.

Figure 12: IBB's NEB values

2.6.4. Jastrebarsko – Croatia | REGEA

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
City Administration Headquarters, City of Jastrebarsko, Croatia	16,683	1 building, 3 floors, 570 m ² , built in 1915 Always in use as an office
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance modernisation and preservation of heritage buildings sustainably 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repurpose and enhance the building's usage - Integrate digital solutions for effective management - Enhance availability and social significance - Considering broader community impact 	

Site-specific Context

The pilot project focuses on the City Administration Headquarters of Jastrebarsko, located in an area protected by Cultural Heritage Regulation. Jastrebarsko, with a rich historical heritage dating back to 1249, includes a market established in the 13th century. The city's well-preserved urban matrix from the 18th and 19th centuries and subsequent developments contribute to its historical significance. Situated 35 km from Zagreb, Jastrebarsko has a population of 16,683 and offers various nearby natural and cultural attractions, such as the Ornithological Reserve Crna Mlaka and Plešivica

wine road. The city administration building, constructed in 1915 and renovated in 1987, features a classical historical style with notable architectural details.

Vision

The vision involves disseminating innovative concepts across public structures and implementing energy-efficient refurbishments, emphasising a multifunctional use of building courtyards and integrating digitalisation into building management. The pilot building for the INHERIT project in the city centre serves as a model for broader emulation, aiming to transform and enhance the surrounding area and inspire similar initiatives in other cities throughout Croatia.

REGEA involves opening the pilot to the public to bolster community involvement and social inclusion, fostering new social connections, and leveraging the role and potential of cultural heritage in sustainable urban development while evaluating innovative INHERIT solutions.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

The pilot faces challenges such as limited community awareness of technology, stakeholder engagement, and ensuring long-term maintenance of the renovated building.

Stakeholders and End Users

Efforts are underway to educate and inform community members, including stakeholder mapping. Identified end user groups, such as the Head of Department for Economy and EU Funds and the local community, stand to gain specific benefits, including educational programs, cultural tourism, and enhanced social connections. In the initial mapping there were 22 stakeholders and 6 end users identified.

Table 10: Initial mapping for the pilot in Jastrebarsko by the consortium partner REGEA

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Jastrebarsko	1	1	1	2	---	3	1	---	11	2
Level	2	2	3	2	---	1	2	---	2 4 5	3

Social Inclusion and Diversity

The pilot case's renovation focuses on energy efficiency and public accessibility, advancing sustainability and community engagement in the region. Opening the space to the public fosters' inclusion by providing a venue for gatherings and cultural activities and by promoting a more connected community. The project balances environmental goals with community well-being working on a positive precedent for future urban initiatives.

NEB Values

The modernisation and conservation of the city administration centre by REGEA encompasses all three NEB values: togetherness, sustainability, and beauty. The mapping was conducted during an online meeting on a whiteboard, showing high ambitions in working with the NEB as a framework. Specifically, inclusivity and beautification are highlighted as guiding ambitions. Furthermore, the need of going beyond disciplines is guiding for the local team, more than aspects related to sustainability. The focus on inclusivity was repeated during second meeting dedicated to mapping NEB aspects in the project.

Figure 13: REGEA's NEB values

2.6.5. Metz – France | BOUYGUES IMMOBILIER SA

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
Le Printemps de Metz landmark building, City of Metz, France	120,874	1 four-sided block building, 4 floors, 12,186 m ² (8,001 m ² project site / land 415 m ²), created in 1909 Formerly shopping mall, now planned: Mixed private housing and commercial use
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mixed-use spaces: blend shops with residential units - Revitalise city centre to attract families - Sustainable focus: thermal insulation, double-glazed windows, heat pumps - Eco-friendly: reuse materials, promote energy efficiency 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urban green initiatives: Ground floor fully vegetated, promoting social atmosphere - Patios for daylight, fostering well-lit communal environment - Social emphasis on a community-oriented living space 	

Site-specific Context

Metz, located in northeast France, is undergoing a significant urban revitalisation effort by converting a historic department store into residential housing, aligning with the city's broader plan for urban conservation. Originally constructed in the early 20th century, the building's sandstone façade is emblematic of Metz's architectural heritage. Over time, it has undergone renovations to adapt to changing needs and will now accommodate 89 residential units, commercial spaces, and parking facilities. Formerly owned by the French retailer "Le Printemps" the property was a prominent commercial landmark in the city until 2021.

Vision

At BOUYGUES, the vision is to refurbish a renowned building into top-tier, eco-friendly residences while upholding its historical significance. Situated in the heart of Metz, this building, formerly a distinguished department store, boasts a facade crafted from Vosges sandstone and Jaumont stone. The project aims for lasting efficiency and high-quality housing tailored to modern needs. The partner is committed to addressing local requirements through thorough renovation and the inclusion of shops and green spaces. Emphasising nature and biodiversity, the design incorporates patios for natural light and vegetal patches to infuse greenery into the urban landscape. Establishing strong community ties with future residents and neighbours is crucial for fostering a tranquil environment, aligning with the project's core values.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

Achieving the goals comes with challenges. Establishing community bonds with neighbours is crucial for fostering tranquillity. Promoting commercial spaces in the city centre is vital for local

engagement. During construction, managing temporary uses is essential to maintain functionality and community appeal. A key challenge lies in project planning, with ongoing construction requiring clear communication with stakeholders to manage adjustments effectively.

Stakeholders and End Users

Stakeholders such as Metz City, Inspire Metz, Bouygues Immobilier, the Metz Tourism Office, Architecte des Bâtiments de France (ABF), Les Ecoporteurs, and the Centre Pompidou play vital roles in the development of Metz. Metz City oversees governance, while Inspire Metz fosters cultural and economic growth. Bouygues Immobilier leads the building transformation in line with urban objectives. The Metz Tourism Office promotes city attractions, and ABF ensures architectural preservation. Les Ecoporteurs focus on eco-friendly initiatives, and the Centre Pompidou enriches culture. Implementation of the project benefits various end users, with shop tenants gaining from the prime location and potential clientele, while Bouygues Immobilier anticipates profit from residential unit sales. Additionally, the project addresses community housing needs by providing secure and comfortable living spaces. In the initial phase there were 21 stakeholders and five end users identified.

Table 11: Initial mapping for the pilot in Metz by the consortium partner BOUYGUES

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Metz	1	7	---	3	2	---	1	---	5	2
Level	2	1 2 3 4 5	---	5	3	---	2	---	2 4	4 5

Social Inclusion and Diversity

The region has a notable immigrant population from Eastern Europe, underscoring the need for deeper socio-demographic research to comprehensively grasp and tackle issues related to social inclusion and diversity. Understanding the distinct requirements and viewpoints of these immigrants is vital for nurturing an inclusive community and tailoring housing initiatives to accommodate the diverse demographics of the region.

NEB Values

The NEB values that are reflected in the redesign of le Printemps de Metz are: beauty, sustainability, and togetherness. Specifically, sustainability is targeted by the local partner, with focus on the introduction of the circular approach as part of the transformation efforts. Also, the aspect of beautification plays a vital role, followed by inclusivity as less targeted ambition at this stage. Similar attitude is reflected in the working principles. With the ambition of working across levels and being interdisciplinary being more advanced than triggering participatory processes, identified as the basic ambition of consulting the process with the stakeholders. In second meeting dedicated to the NEB (IV 2024), again “sustainability” was highlighted as most important value, and multi-level engagement as the driving working principle.

Figure 14: BOUYGUES' NEB values

2.6.6. Riga – Latvia | RPR

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
Concert Hall, City of Riga, Latvia	860,142	1 building, 3 floors, 635.9 m ² , build in 1780 (reconstructed in 1980) Formally church, nowadays a concert hall
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyse renovation process and future maintenance - Test data-driven energy management methods - Implement solutions for improved thermal comfort 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage with local choir community for strong connections - Prioritise inclusion, considering individuals with disabilities - Implement diverse strategies for accessibility improvements 	

Site-specific Context

Riga, Latvia's capital and largest city, boasts a UNESCO World Heritage Site historical centre renowned for its Art Nouveau and 19th-century wooden architecture. It is situated at the mouth of the Daugava River on the Gulf of Riga where it meets the Baltic Sea. Notable for its extensive collection of Art Nouveau buildings dating from 1896 to 1913, Riga's architectural influence extends across the Baltic region. Landmarks like the Ave Sol concert hall, formerly St. Peter and Pavel Church, showcase the city's rich cultural heritage and architectural diversity.

Vision

The ambitious vision of transforming the pilot building in Riga into an inclusive space involves collaborating with a local disability advocacy organisation to create a more empathetic environment that addresses the diverse needs of individuals with disabilities. Simultaneously aligning with ongoing public transport accessibility improvements anticipates a seamlessly connected urban landscape, fostering societal inclusion, and contributing to a more enriched and harmonious community in Riga.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

As the initiative endeavours to embrace social challenges and diversity, anticipated concerns include navigating the diverse needs and perspectives within the disability community, despite collaborative efforts with the advocacy organisation in Riga. Balancing varied requirements to ensure genuine inclusion in the renovated building may pose a delicate task. Additionally, coordinating the synchronisation of infrastructure improvements with the building's renovation, managing public expectations, and addressing communication challenges will be essential for the initiative's success in promoting a more inclusive and accessible environment for all.

Stakeholders and End Users

The project engages various stakeholders, including academic institutions, governmental bodies, financial institutions, NGOs, users of the Ave Sol building, and media outlets. End users, such as choirs in the Ave Sol building, will benefit from improved facilities, while the National Cultural Heritage Administration ensures the preservation of its cultural significance. In the initial phase there were 14 stakeholders and eight end users identified.

Table 12: Initial mapping for the pilot in Riga by the consortium partner RPR

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Riga	---	2	1	---	---	---	1	1	8	1
Level	---	3 5	2	---	---	---	5	1	2 5	3

Social Inclusion and Diversity

The initiative demonstrates a commitment to inclusion by partnering with a disability advocacy organisation in Riga, emphasising the importance of addressing the diverse needs within the disability community. Through this collaboration, the project aims to gain insights into the challenges faced by people with disabilities informing a more empathetic and comprehensive approach to accessibility.

NEB Values

In the realisation and implementation of the project, RPR is primarily concerned with beauty and togetherness, with less focus on sustainability, during the initial stage of INHERIT. Across all three working principles there is a visible interest in co-developing, working across levels and being interdisciplinary in the project.

Figure 15: RPR's NEB values

2.6.7. Valladolid – Spain | CARTIF

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of Building
Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. del Prado', Castile and León, Valladolid, SPAIN	301,872	1 building, 4 floors (excl. basement and mezzanine), 55.258 m ² , build in 1440 First built as monastery (with different uses through the century like royal printing, prison, psychiatric hospital), now: Headquarter od Ministry of Culture, Tourism and Sports and the Ministry of Education
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited adoption of H-BIM observed across Europe - Demonstrate effective use of public funds for proper renovations aligned with sustainability standards, low-energy performance requirements, and digital solutions 	
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community involvement: Engage residents for ownership and aligned activities - Sustainability: Implement comprehensive green technologies and practices - H-BIM model: Simulate renovations and anticipate energy performance - Showcase effective fund utilisation for sustainable solutions 	

Site-specific Context

Castile and León, located in northwest Spain, is known for its low population density and aging demographic, with Valladolid serving as the regional capital. The region boasts eleven UNESCO

World Heritage Sites, including the Cortes of León of 1188, considered the birthplace of modern parliamentarism. The monastery, a national monument since 1877, was restored in the 1980s and now houses government offices. As part of the INHERIT project, it serves as a pioneering example for developing an H-BIM DT model, mandated by EU regulations since 2018 for public buildings, despite challenges in the conservative cultural heritage sector.

Vision

CARTIF's vision is to create a model that can be widely replicated. With around 70% of cultural heritage buildings in Europe open to the public, the initiative has the potential for broad impact. Spain, particularly Castilla and Leon, known for its rich cultural heritage, stands to benefit, given its significant UNESCO world heritage sites. The digital model developed in the pilot program could provide valuable insights for preserving and managing these assets sustainably.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

The primary challenge is preserving the cultural and historical value of heritage buildings, compounded by a lack of real commitment to complying with the European directive 2014/24/EU for BIM Level 2, due to the unique and diverse nature of cultural heritage. Professionals engaged with the H-BIM model, including architects and civil engineers, may express interest in its refinement, but its technical complexity may hinder broader accessibility. While professionals can simulate interventions digitally, this complexity may limit practical use for citizens without specialised knowledge. Clear communication of the model's purpose to citizens is crucial for aligning with the project's goal of drafting a visionary renovation plan for the monastery. H-BIM projects help to ensure that cultural heritage is preserved for future generations, maintaining a tangible connection to the past in an increasingly digital world, thereby fostering a sense of identity and continuity within communities. Additionally, facilitate deeper engagement with cultural heritage by enhancing their understanding and appreciation of historical contexts upon a highly skilled work.

Stakeholders and End Users

The project collaborates with stakeholders from both the public and private sectors, including entities like the Consejería de Cultura, Turismo y Deporte and the Dirección General de Patrimonio Cultural. Private sector engagement is facilitated through associations like Clúster de Hábitat Eficiente (AEICE). The stakeholders benefit from leveraging innovative technologies and community engagement to preserve cultural heritage, promote tourism, and reinforce cultural identity in the region, thereby contributing to sustainable development and heritage preservation. In the initial phase there were three stakeholders and two end users identified.

Table 13: Initial mapping for the pilot in Valladolid by the consortium partner CARTIF

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Valladolid	---	1	---	---	---	---	---	---	2	---
Level	---	1	---	---	---	---	---	---	5	---

Social Inclusion and Diversity

While professionals may possess the technical expertise to engage with the Heritage Building Information Modelling, social involvement in the corresponding highly technical process is absolutely limited. Linking H-BIM with social inclusiveness and diversity involves using professional digital tools to enhance the accessibility and representation of cultural heritage for all community segments. INHERIT developments on H-BIM are a first step that could be employed beyond the project's lifespan to create accessible, virtual experiences of heritage sites, allowing people with physical disabilities or those living far from such sites to explore and learn about cultural landmarks comfortably from their own homes. By doing so, H-BIM not only acts as a custodian of architectural accuracy but also becomes a platform for inclusive cultural dialogue and education, enriching the appreciation of heritage through a lens that respects and reflects societal diversity.

NEB Values

The mapping of the NEB values and working principles was conducted collectively on MIRO board, based on the methodology described in the NEB toolbox. CARTIF's main focus on the renovation of the monastery is on sustainability, specifically on fostering circular approach. Also, beauty, to connect with the site's uniqueness, is part of the ambitions. Less focus is on inclusivity and participatory processes, both being addressed at a basic level. The local team wishes furthermore to foster interdisciplinary approach.

Figure 16: CARTIF's NEB values

2.6.8. Visby – Sweden | UU

Pilot Case	City Population	Type of City														
Historic city centre of Visby, Sweden	7,500	<p>Hanseatic town wall circled medieval city centre, » 0.92 km², approximately 1,250 building (200 heritage designated and protected), built from 13th century</p> <p>Different uses through the centuries</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Year of Construction</th> <th>Number of Buildings</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1200 – 1550</td> <td>33</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1550 – 1699</td> <td>35</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1700 – 1799</td> <td>443</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1800 – 1899</td> <td>372</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1900 – 1999</td> <td>357</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2000 -</td> <td>16</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Year of Construction	Number of Buildings	1200 – 1550	33	1550 – 1699	35	1700 – 1799	443	1800 – 1899	372	1900 – 1999	357	2000 -	16
Year of Construction	Number of Buildings															
1200 – 1550	33															
1550 – 1699	35															
1700 – 1799	443															
1800 – 1899	372															
1900 – 1999	357															
2000 -	16															
Objective/s (Based on GA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Address climate change through mitigation and adaptation - Maintain local population with affordable housing and community support - Encourage engagement of Gotland residents in Visby's activities 															
Issues of Interest (Results from bilateral brainstorming)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated framework balances heritage preservation with sustainability goals - Enhanced decision support for distinct stakeholders groups - Increased awareness fosters community engagement 															

Site-specific Context

Visby, located on Gotland Island in the Baltic Sea, encompasses an inhabited historic town designated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. It features a well-preserved medieval ring wall and 1100 historic buildings reflecting various architectural phases. Visby's distinctive medieval structures require building consent from municipal authorities for any alterations. Despite being a major tourist destination, the challenge lies in balancing tourism with maintaining a liveable city, emphasising sustainable tourism management. The case study focuses on showcasing INHERIT services on representative buildings, including one medieval public building owned by the municipality of Gotland for illustrative purposes.

Vision

The vision aims to raise awareness of knowledge advancement potential and position Visby as a national pilot for developing a smart and renewable energy system. Through categorisation of existing building stock and life cycle cost calculations, Visby becomes a testing ground for sustainable energy solutions, aligning with national objectives.

The vision for social responsibility in the Visby case aims to raise awareness among all relevant stakeholders regarding the diverse impact activities have on the potential transformation of the existing built environment into a future sustainable and liveable city. This entails expanding the objectives outlined in the strategy for the world heritage site of the medieval city of Visby. The vision encompasses not only the conservation, maintenance, and management of the built environment but also advocates for a broader approach towards building a resilient and sustainable city.

Anticipated Challenges and Concerns

Navigating evolving technologies, policy dynamics, and stakeholder engagement poses complex challenges in the energy transition context. Addressing financial considerations, community acceptance, and integrating smart technologies are key concerns, especially given the diverse historic building stock with strong heritage protection.

Stakeholders and End Users

Stakeholders involved include property owners, municipalities, organisations hosting activities in Visby, and the university and research sector. Each group contributes unique perspectives and expertise, with property owners pivotal in transformation. Benefits for end users include informed decision-making and efficiency improvements for regional authorities. In the initial mapping phase, there were 11 stakeholders and four end users identified.

Table 14: Initial mapping for the pilot in Visby by the consortium partner UU

STH Group	Civil Society Organisation (CSO)	Association	Universities / Higher Education	Community	Site Owner & Metropolitan Municipality	Education incl. Schools / Lifelong Professional	Cultural Creative Industry (CCI)	Media / Journalists / Digital Influencer	Public Authorities	Other
Visby	1	1	1	1	---	---	---	---	4	3
Level	5	4	3	2	---	---	---	---	4 5	3

Social Inclusion and Diversity

Upcoming initiatives focus on social inclusiveness and diversity, involving participants such as property owner organisations, museum administrators, and advocates for Visby's diverse community. A collaborative workshop is planned to promote inclusion and diversity, ensuring diverse stakeholder voices are recognised and integrated.

NEB Values

During the mapping activity inspired by the NEB Toolbox and conducted online in November 2023, the following ambitions have been identified. The local partner in the transformation process is interested in going beyond disciplines, co-developing changes and working across levels. Furthermore, sustainability and the beauty of the entire historic city centre are associated with more advanced ambitions. Less in focus, at the initial stage of INHERIT, is inclusivity of various stakeholders and participatory processes.

Figure 17: UU's NEB values

3. Social Labs Methodological Handbook

This section is designed to support INHERIT partners implementing the eight INHERIT social labs with practical instructions. The handbook is also designed to support future social labs working in the field of cultural heritage.

3.1. Interplay of Social Labs, MSF & S-LCA as Co-Creation Instruments

To support the collaborative and iterative problem-solving process and distilling improved solutions or new knowledge from the experiments, different feedback methods in the lab and the MSF are applied.

While the INHERIT social labs bring also include representatives from the communities or civil society, the MSF invites operators, owners, decision makers (OOD) from a transregional or European level to contribute to the co-creation process.

In addition, a S-LCA fosters change, and spillover effects impacted by the pilots and their lab activities. The transition will be attuned to tackle social and ethical challenges, including privacy issues, rights of children and juveniles, social inclusion of minorities and vulnerable groups, and diversity, including gender balance and intergenerational equity.

Figure 18 helps to illustrate this workflow once more. The scope of activities (relatedly: objectives) triggered by the social labs include the building of a joint understanding on the social lab process and its transformative potential, the joint definition of pathways, how each pilot together with its stakeholders could improve its operation of the cultural heritage building and the stocktaking of current needs, issues, and performance practices in this regard. The S-LCA, on the other hand, adds the monitoring perspective to this continuum, making sure that progress is captured, or, in the other case, any challenges and difficulties are anticipated as early as possible.

Figure 18: INHERIT social lab transition and the interdependency to S-LCA

3.2. Definition and underlying Concepts of the INHERIT Social Labs

In addition to the short definition given in the introduction chapter, the following **working definition is applied in INHERIT**:

INHERIT social labs are established in the context of the eight INHERIT pilots and focus on mutual learning in an experimental environment, in which stakeholders from science, innovation, CH practice and civil society come together to develop and test solutions based on a common understanding of the problem to make them socially robust. Identified individuals or organisations shall have an interest or concern related to the objectives of INHERIT.

The INHERIT social labs are viewed as containers within complex cultural, ecological, economic, and social challenges linked to cultural heritage. In general, the social approach connects diverse disciplines and people, who are affected by shared problems in various ways. The methodology provides space for doing transdisciplinary interventions and social experiments in a practical context, where researchers, professional experts, stakeholders such as neighbourhoods, or communities, and concerned groups initiate together actions focused on tackling challenges **without being restricted by a predetermined process** (Hassan 2014). Unlike closed laboratories, social labs are embedded in the real world. This enables the **testing and prototypes in actual social settings**, promoting the uptake of results (Marschalek et al. 2023).

Another asset of the social lab interventions in INHERIT is to accelerate processes that can enhance

the value creation (e.g. OECD 2021, Golinelli 2014, Dümcke and Gnedovsky 2013) by addressing the social dimension or prepare the ground for spill-over effects in cultural and creative industries or the 3rd sector.

In this context, **social value creation** refers to the positive impact that CH can have on communities or neighbourhoods and individuals. It involves preserving, promoting, and utilising cultural assets of the INHERIT project in ways that benefit people and contribute to their well-being or to social innovation.

Social value creation for cultural heritage refers to the positive impact that e.g. CH sites and its buildings can have on society, communities, and individuals. It involves preserving, promoting, and utilising cultural assets in ways that benefit communities and contribute to their well-being. This addresses the following aspects of social value creation in INHERIT:

- **Education:** CH sites and buildings, artifacts, and traditions provide educational opportunities. They help people learn about history, art, architecture, and the values of different cultures. Museums, historical sites, and cultural events contribute to the public awareness
- **Community Identity:** CH fosters a sense of identity within communities and connects people to shared history. Local events, traditional crafts, and storytelling events strengthen community bonds.
- **Tourism and economic development:** CH sites and buildings attract tourists, generating revenue for local economies. Tourists spend money on accommodations, food, and souvenirs. Preservation efforts and tourism-related jobs contribute to economic growth of the locality or region.
- **Social Inclusion and well-being:** Cultural activities promote social inclusion by bringing people together. They create spaces for dialogue, collaboration, and mutual understanding. Participating in cultural events enhances well-being, reduces stress, and improves mental health.
- **Environmental stewardship:** Some cultural heritage sites are closely tied to natural landscapes. By preserving these sites, we also protect the environment. Traditional ecological knowledge and sustainable practices can contribute to environmental conservation.
- **Intergenerational transmission:** Passing down cultural traditions from one generation to the next helps maintain cultural diversity. Family encounters, oral histories, and craftsmanship are examples of intergenerational transmission.

To foster these heterogenous needs, **social labs** – defined as **qualitative research approach and research setting**, equally – and co-creation methods follow a practical orientation and will be further specified according to the needs emerging in the social labs. Processes in the social lab include pre-designed obligatory activities; to support the participatory mode of collaboration with stakeholders

and to foster an engagement culture, social labs allow open ended processes. This enables volunteer participants to raise further questions or issues coming from real life setting or support the decision making, which methods and activities shall be implemented.

INHERIT social labs provide opportunities for transdisciplinary cooperation between researchers, professionals and volunteer participants. Volunteering for participatory research and co-creation can be driven by various motivations:

Beside the interest to learn new or to try out new skills, it can be the interest to make a difference. INHERIT social labs offer an opportunity to foster social change and make a positive impact on a real-world problem in the pilots.

In this context, it is important to meet the participants on an equal footing and build partnerships. Volunteers are expected to contribute continuously and experience their impact in form of interim results made with the help of their co-creative contribution or their user-centric feedback, which shapes an INHERIT technology solution or service.

3.3. Main Steps and Activities in the Social Labs

The following table provides an overview on INHERIT social lab activities and events that are foreseen until M14. At this point a follow-up task will start to work on the co-creation of socially robust results and services. A further outlook in a more general manner is given until M39, which is the end month of all co-creation activities.

Table 15: INHERIT social lab activities and events

Phases Sequences	Month	Activities	(Expected) Outcomes
Conducting context	M2 – M3	Bilateral interviews between ZSI and the pilot partners addressing needs and determining social, ecological, legal, technical and economic constraints.	Synthesise the gained context from the interviews which will feed into the INHERIT stakeholder engagement strategy.
Train-the-trainer workshop	M5	Detailed presentation of the materials provided for the social lab events and their application, alongside guidance on the methodology pilots will employ during their respective events.	Ensures that pilot trainers are equipped with the necessary knowledge and resources to effectively facilitate the social labs, fostering a conducive environment for collaborative problem-solving and innovation.
Social labs Toolkit	M5	A collection of resources, materials, and tools designed and made available to assist the pilot partners during the implementation of the social labs.	Empower them with essential resources and guidance, streamlining their understanding, it enhances efficiency while ensuring standardised approaches and improved outcomes.

Social Labs Methodological Handbook, high-level requirements

Kick-off of the social labs, workshops Vol.1	M8 – M10	Eight kick-off events organised by pilot partners, collaborating with stakeholders from different disciplines to assess their needs and perspectives.	Bring together different stakeholders, fosters cross-disciplinary dialogue and lays the groundwork for collaborative problem-solving initiatives within the pilots.
Cross-fertilisation workshop	M10	Critical friend feedback, knowledge and experience sharing workshop after the completion of the first social lab events.	Reflect collectively on the outcomes and insights gained from the social lab kick-offs, learn from each other's experiences and best practices and develop further strategies for the upcoming social lab workshops. Further workshops for exchange can follow due to needs.
Lab workshop Vol.2, one per pilot	M10 – M18	Co-Creation workshop	These events intend to strengthen stakeholder collaboration with the pilot partners and the contribution to socially robust INHERIT results. Workshop 2 of this series includes a capacity building module on co-creation addressed to the social lab participants
Lab workshop Vol. 3, one per pilot	M14 – M39	Co-Creation workshop	See above According to the different scope and needs of pilots, lab workshop cycle 2 to 3 can overlap on the timeline
Support, networking and dissemination events	On demand until M39	Co-Creation, capacity building, networking, dissemination	Every pilot is expected to implement a least 3 co-creation workshops; in addition, support events can build a stronger partnership with multi-stakeholders including communities.
Cross-Fertilisation and Co-analysis workshop	On demand until M39	Critical friend feedback, review quality management and assurance	These events can be implemented together with the MSF. The MSF expert pool can help to gain cross-disciplinary feedback and to support the quality management and the meaningfulness of process and results.

3.4. Main Objectives

INHERIT social labs harnesses the heterogeneous perspective of transdisciplinary teams and multi-stakeholders to identify solutions for real world problems found within the pilot communities or regions. It fosters different forms of knowledge and makes tacit knowledge and transformation

knowledge of communities visible to reach technology-related, social or transversal objectives, equally.

In general, INHERIT social labs aim to enable

- collaborative knowledge production,
- co-created strategies, services, and solutions,
- innovation partnerships involving local communities and end users of INHERIT solutions in transdisciplinary expert teams.

In addition to these main objectives labs shall

- support a social (and sustainable) value creation in accordance with the framework ISO 26000
- and provide a space for co-creation to impact local ecosystems.

The types of problems that these labs can address are diverse, ranging from local community challenges to specific research questions concerning the cultural heritage and cross-sectors.

During several internal co-design activities, pilot partners reflected major objectives (defined during the proposal phase) regarding social issues and developed complementary objectives linked to the social fabric.

3.5. Design and Set-up of the INHERIT Social Labs and joint Activities

The INHERIT Social Lab process spans a period of over three years during WP2 (M1–39). During this period, **a minimum of 3 workshops** or activities with external stakeholders or end users are organised **in each lab**. The social lab process includes the phases of (1) initiation & preliminary research, (2) preparation and stakeholder recruitment, (3) workshops and (4) documentation & exploitation after the workshops.

A total of **25 co-creation sessions** will be organised by pilot lead partners. According to the dynamic and partly open character of the INHERIT co-creation process, this is divided into **24 workshops with multi-stakeholders** in the context of the labs and **one co-creation workshop with end users** to shape the INHERIT technical solutions.

The first phase involves investing resources to support the co-creation and implementation of pilots capable of generating impact. The recruitment process and the field research are the main steps (as well as phase 4) in the second phase and starts from the beginning. Social Labs bring together persons from HQ with specific expertise, needs, concerns, and expectations. Participants are empowered to act on their own expectations and towards creative ideas. In the third phase, there is a series of workshops with co-creation, collaborative knowledge production and further engaging activities. They are designed to engage participants, explore the context, and facilitate new

perspectives on the problems. The final goal of the workshops and engagement activities is to select one or more ideas for real-world use and pilot testing. Transferred to the INHERIT social labs, this comprises six main objectives linked to activities:

- Context and user studies and determining social, ecological, legal, or technical and economic constraints, updating the INHERIT stakeholder engagement strategy,
- Raising awareness and building knowledge on INHERIT through citizen science or participatory community-based research and transferring knowledge through science communication,
- Using techniques such as World Café and Mapping Walk to contribute to the stakeholders needs and the status of the pilots,
- Co-designing cultural management innovations involving CH practitioners and researchers,
- Testing research and learning scenarios for the INHERIT CH management capacity building,
- Building a local and transregional INHERIT community of interest.

Additional objectives and activities will be co-designed with lab participants addressing site- and community-specific needs and interests.

To enable lab participants to be creative on finding solutions to real-world problems, INHERIT social labs follow a structured concept with clear roles and responsibilities. The lab managing team includes a manager, a facilitator, and a community representative. Lab managers are the main contact persons responsible for recruiting and communicating with participants, taking care of coordination, supporting lab activities and logistics. Facilitators are the responsible moderators during the lab workshops, who choose methods and event formats to facilitate the dialogue between lab participants.

Figure 19: Collaboration of stakeholders and the responsible persons for social labs

The kick-off events host representatives from all stakeholder groups along QH scheme identified in the tentative stakeholder mapping between M1 to M3.

Based on this initial stakeholder mapping a train-the-trainer workshop was implemented to prepare pilot lead partners for their role as hosts and managers of the INHERIT labs and to start the identification and recruitment of multi-stakeholders and potential end users.

Figure 20: INHERIT social lab approach

Overall, the INHERIT social labs are composed of four main activities:

- conducting context and needs studies and determining social, ecological, legal, technical and economic constraints feeding back into the overall engagement strategy;
- co-creating innovations involving end users such as CH practitioners, policy makers and further stakeholders from QH,
- conducting experiments in the pilot case scenarios providing a testbed for technology
- including a co-assessment implemented by pilot leaders, supported by the WP lead partner.

3.6. Workshop Methods to kick-off the INHERIT Social Labs

The first lab workshop in each INHERIT pilot uses a pre-defined set of methods, while the design and methods of the follow-up workshops will align with the needs of the social lab participants, their capacity, and interests. This can support the motivation of volunteer participants to contribute more continuously. Methods of follow-up events will be chosen accordingly to lab objectives or lab

projects co-designed with participants during the lab kick-off phase.

To build a robust lab in each pilot, the kick-off events take advantage of approaches from “Art of Hosting” (AoH) to access knowledge of experts and non-expert participants as well as to enable transdisciplinary thinking. AoH is a methodology that can be used to support participatory leadership for facilitating group processes, knowledge production, and decision making with multi-stakeholder groups.

The first methods, World Café (obligatory) and mapping walk (optional), are foreseen to be implemented during the lab kick-off events.

3.6.1. World Café

The method is foreseen to support a group dialog for a context analysis including the perspective of stakeholders and the needs assessment of multi-stakeholders in the initial co-creation phase of INHERIT. It is useful to bring different disciplines, scientists and practitioners, and professionals together and to build first bonds between volunteer participants and researchers from INHERIT project supporting a more sustainable commitment to the INHERIT co-creation process. The method can quickly enable conversations between multi-stakeholders from QH representing different interests, needs and knowledge and helps to discuss different topics in a short time.

World Café method is a structured conversational process for knowledge sharing in which participants discuss a topic at several small tables like those in a café. Although pre-defined questions are agreed upon at the beginning, outcomes or solutions are not decided in advance. The assumption is that collective discussion can shift participants conceptions and encourage collective action.

The format imitates a café setting, where small groups with a **minimum of 4** (representing the QH) **to 12 stakeholders** are all conversing together around tables. Small groups are in conversation about an important issue, for example site-specific needs, local interests, regional challenges. After the first conversation, someone stays at the table as ‘host’ while the others move to a new table, taking their previous conversations with them. In this way, the threads of the various conversations are brought together, and a big picture of the discussions can arise. The World Café is planned to discuss two to three sets of questions focusing on the stakeholders, their needs, and optionally on the relevance of the NEB.

It is also recommended to discuss the interests and to ask the INHERIT social lab participants to define **joint objectives for the future activities of the labs**. This can be done instead of the table three discussion on NEB values or after the Café setting in the plenary.

To gain comparable results related to the context analysis and needs assessment, all INHERIT social labs are requested to use the method during the kick-off event. In any case, as there is a certain flexibility needed due to the different nature of INHERIT pilots, the method can be aligned with site specific needs. The following figure shows the table setting and related questions. More questions were presented during the train-the-trainer workshop and were aligned with the specific nature of

the eight pilots.

STAKEHOLDERS AND POTENTIAL USERS

Draw a stakeholder landscape:

- Who is the target audience? Whom else shall we involve?
- What is the expected engagement level? Why?

NEEDS-POTENTIAL-CONSTRAINTS

- Which solutions are already in use?
- What (else) is needed?
- What is in it for me?
- How can we make a broader audience benefit from the project?

NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS (optional)

- What is in it for me?
- What do we need to consider?

Figure 21: The World Café method table questions

The implementation of this method is foreseen for all INHERIT social lab kick-off workshops.

- **Participant group/s:** experts and non-experts from QH
- **Space:** onsite, with some limitations also online
- **Duration:** 1.5h to half day (depends on the number of participants and questions)

3.6.2. Mapping Walk

The method is recommended to those INHERIT pilots with a central link to communities and neighbourhoods and the need to build partnerships with citizens as volunteer co-creators. It involves social lab participants working together to create maps that reflect their collective understanding of a particular site or issue linked to the INHERIT pilot or the heritage building. Mapping walk are process-oriented and aim to engage participants actively in the research or co-creation process. The formats encourage volunteer participants to look at their environment and other people from different perspectives. By involving diverse groups of people (e.g. from QH), these

methods can lead to more inclusive and indicative outcomes in co-creation projects. This includes variations of the method such as the

- **Neighbourhood mapping:** Participants explore the neighbourhoods of the heritage building and map out significant places, routes, and landmarks, which are related to the INHERIT pilot. This process can reveal shared values, concerns, and aspirations within the community.
- **Asset mapping:** Participants identify and document the tangible and intangible assets of a place or the community, such as skills, resources, relationships, and cultural landmarks.
- **Transect mapping:** This is another variation of a mapping walk used to gather more detailed information about a specific place or site by systematically surveying and recording observations across it. The resulting map provides a visual representation of the collected data, making it easier to understand and analyse patterns, relationships, and trends. Through shared experiences and discussions, transect mapping can help build consensus among participants on priorities and actions. The route must be planned carefully, participants have to be provided with the necessary tools like maps, GPS devices, or notepads, and a clear process for recording observations. After the walk, a debriefing with participants will take place to discuss findings and next steps that can reveal further critical points.
- **Shared walks:** This approach focuses on the act of walking together to foster social encounters and interactions – the documentation could be short and general or detailed using different media.

INHERIT pilot partners can mix mapping approaches given site-specific needs and desired outputs. The shared walk is also an icebreaker best implemented in pairs of walkers to overcome quickly potential hesitance of participants to talk, while the transect walk foresees a more structured route and comprehensive documentation of the walk by the participants.

- **Participants group/s:** mix of expert and no-experts, representatives from QH, citizens
- **Space:** on-site
- **Duration:** 3h to half day

3.7. Social Lab Toolkit

The toolkit is a resource of materials designed to support the creation and operation of social labs. It contains instructions for using and applying diverse support materials in the INHERIT social labs. The collection is hands-on and enables the stakeholder and community engagement activities and the practical set-up of events and co-creation activities. It can be used to plan, kick-off and facilitate, and to document the workshop series in all five pilot cases. The toolkit is available online on the project data cloud and includes the following templates and materials:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INHERIT lab kick-off plan (see Appendix) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event documentation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation letter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • World Café table documentation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General INHERIT project presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional workshop templates
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agenda template 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ice-breaker exercise (presentation or template on demand)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participant list template 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed consent
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotional material (poster etc.)

Figure 22: Path to social labs toolkit and documentation on the storage cloud

3.8. Code of Conduct

To establish a balanced communication in the labs and other pilot activities, it is obligatory to introduce a Code of Conduct (CoC) on seriousness, fairness, and transparency during the kick-off INHERIT Social Labs with citizen science and co-creation. The CoC is presented at the beginning of the kick-off event and made available whenever new stakeholders participate in the labs.

The INHERIT consortium communicates, when they are going to decide, how stakeholders' contributions will be considered, and what kind of feedback will be given. The INHERIT consortium partners implementing social labs and workshop activities are asked to take orientation on the following CoC principles:

- Lab participant's needs and interests are at heart of the INHERIT social labs: lab hosts are asked to align objectives of co-creation and research interventions with the interests, expectations and needs of the stakeholders. They have a stake in INHERIT project and pilots.
- The lab managers and facilitators should ensure that all participants are well informed and that they respect the seriousness of the co-creation process.
- Community members or citizens have equal opportunity to participate in the lab!
- It needs be taken care of that no participants are unfairly impacted by the lab and the co-creation activities!

- It must be ensured that all participants are provided with clear and barrier-free information. There are three stages of information: before the process, during the process and after the process.
- Findings need to be presented in an accessible, meaningful, and timely way to citizens and community members!
- It is important that all participants have the same chance to have their say. Therefore, the process must be designed and implemented in a way that everybody – irrespective of age, sex, income – can participate equally. It is the moderators' and facilitators' task to ensure a proper implementation of this requirement.
- Pilot lead partners need to know their participants in advance, reminding them, at the start of lab or citizen science workshop, how they can benefit from taking part!
- Protect privacy in the data collection and sharing process! Gain adequate permission (informed consent). Participants need to understand and agree with the way INHERIT plans to use the data.
- The presentation (or presenter) of findings needs to avoid negative social stereotypes in the communication and the materials used in the labs.

To support the continuous commitment of participants, expectations and benefits must be highlighted to the potential INHERIT social lab participants:

- Expand your personal and professional network!
- Learn more about state-of-the-art safeguarding and preservation methods!
- Provide feedback in an early research and design phase for the cultural heritage valorisation in the INHERIT project!
- Identify potential business opportunities in the field of cultural or social entrepreneurship!
- Peer learning – take advantage of the opportunity to exchange ideas with experts from different disciplines and sectors!
- Benefit from building a community of interest during the INHERIT social labs and become part of your local and regional social innovation and green strategy for cultural heritage.

3.9. Seed Money

Lab seed money for participants in a social lab is typically provided to support their engagement in co-creation, experimentation, and prototyping. This seed money can encourage collaboration among lab participants and build a stronger commitment to contribute to the activities in the INHERIT social labs. It fosters partnerships, knowledge sharing, and joint efforts to tackle site-specific problems.

The funds can act as a catalyst, enabling lab participants. to co-design concepts, to test their ideas in a real world setting and refine ideas before scaling them up. They can gather feedback, iterate,

and refine their approaches based on actual user experiences. Participants can use the seed money for tailor-made capacity building, support for graphic design or project shadowing visits and field trips linked to their project acquiring new skills and knowledge relevant to their social innovation projects.

Seed money refers to a funding provided in form of a lump sum for each pilot, which is dedicated to the lab participants to enable specific activities or initiatives aimed at creating positive social impact or to create social innovation. The specific allocation and guidelines for seed money can vary depending on the social lab's objectives and funding sources. It is recommended to provide at least small sums between 500 € and 1500 € at the disposal to lab participants for e.g. citizen science events, catering, travel costs, space rent, materials and logistics costs for exhibitions or CH picnics. In some cases, gift vouchers for books, museums tickets or similar could be an incentive for social lab participants.

4. INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum

4.1. Rationale

The MSF aims to support a culture of engagement based on participatory principles in the INHERIT project and to build

- leadership in creative climate change mitigation solutions
- leadership in the sustainable and sensitive valorisation
- affinity through beauty /aesthetics, sustainability & togetherness

for CH buildings in Europe.

To assure the adaption and uptake of tech and social innovation, INHERIT fosters social lifecycle practices in the context of CH management, which is understood as a green-smart and socially inclusive managerial practices and performance. Moreover, the MSF contributes to an open and accountable decision-making process with the possibility to assess process and results in INHERIT. MSF as well as INHERIT Social lab activities are primed by the main principles of the NEB as a whole way of life,, in the research and innovation process: beauty (or aesthetic), sustainability, togetherness.

In this context, the MSF is also a potential space to discuss and test the NEB values and principles „on the ground” and in a real-world-problem context. MSF participants from different disciplinary backgrounds are brought together in so-called affinity spaces to discuss interests, needs and challenges in the context of the project and its CH buildings. This motivation can form a community of interest and encourages the breakdown of expert knowledge and overcoming barriers such as academic discipline, socio-economic status, education, and age. The MSF enables affinity spaces for a transdisciplinary exchange, including disadvantaged or vulnerable groups and to empower them as change-makers co-shaping and taking advantage of the innovations generated by INHERIT.

The following vision statement³ for the MSF was co-designed by the INHERIT consortium partners in the initial phase of the project addressing the social and participatory potential of CH in INHERIT:

CH is dynamic, for all, and a container for multiple values. Against this background, INHERIT’s innovative practices and technologies shall contribute to creative climate leadership, new strategies for the sensitive valorisation of CH. Furthermore, CH management shall be improved by the reflection of social responsibility and the values of the NEB.

³ Corresponding with the WP2 in the INHERIT project: *STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT, CO-CREATION & SOCIAL INNOVATION FOR THE HERITAGE BUILD ENVIRONMENT*

The INHERIT MSF is a new forum hosted by the EU-funded INHERIT project during the course project to give space for knowledge building, discussion, mutual learning, collaborative problem-solving, consultation and networking, moreover, it seeks to enable new cross-sectoral partnerships.

The MSF comprises meetings, surveys small-scale workshops and presentation and discussion events and an Info Desk to reach out to the INHERIT experts and invites participants to initiate or maximise cooperations.

The topics covered in the MSF can encompass a range of critical areas (state-of the art and niche topics) empowered by the idea of building leadership in the climate change mitigation solutions, in the sustainable valorisation of CH and in the making of NEB values operational valuing the expertise of disadvantaged and vulnerable groups (see also rational above). The potential topics include

- social responsibility and social innovation,
- climate-smart and socially inclusive cultural management,
- the sustainable and sensitive valorisation of cultural heritage,
- innovation in retrofit,
- sustainability strategies and green technologies, and the
- potential of the NEB values “on the ground” including aesthetics (beauty) with its potential to transform life and work settings.

The agenda setting follows a flexible and dynamic approach sourced by the project’s progress and considers the needs, challenges, and the feedback by stakeholders in the INHERIT labs and testbeds.

The MSF is another important engagement instrument of the INHERIT project and complements the work of the INHERIT labs and goes hand in hand with the INHERIT capacity building activities and further capitalisation and exploitation activities in the project.

The MSF empowers the cross-fertilisation of the eight INHERIT social labs on a transregional or an European scale.

Figure 23: The MSF main pillars

4.2. Summary of overarching Objectives and Phases

Due to the agile character of the social labs and the MSF, further objectives can be identified in the discussion and mutual learning activities with stakeholders or end users. The MSF encourages its participants to contribute to the agenda setting and, therefore, contributes to the relevance of INHERIT results both on a societal and a specialist level equally.

Table 16: Major goals of the MSF

Major Goals	General Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To allow on a transregional scale knowledge sharing and cooperation opportunities, both in the co-creation and the application of socially inclusive technical services for CH based on the solutions developed in INHERIT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least biannual events in form with presentation and/or discussion format The first volume starts with a focus on the NEB values.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To create a transdisciplinary expert group from research, innovation, and practice To collaborate with HORIZON sister projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand MSF small scale event/s for cross-fertilisation and critical friend feedback On-demand MSF small scale event/s for critical friend feedback and knowledge transfer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To empower minority perspectives in the MSF: Including marginalised perspectives and finding a common language for mutual negotiation and mutual learning in innovative meeting formats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least one small-scale event with workshop with stakeholder representatives from CSOs mirroring topics of social relevance in the eight pilots or CH buildings in general
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable cross-sectoral innovation partnerships by connecting key stakeholders from the INHERIT labs and further INHERIT project environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least one small-scale (virtual) business breakfasts with stakeholders from different sectors with an interest in green innovation & technology, social responsibility and CH management
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To maximise participation and cooperation and to create a safe space for sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offering the MSF community to give feedback through events or surveys to the INHERIT process, findings and tools.

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To build a community of interest (CoI is a gathering of people assembled around a topic of common interest) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of INHERIT 's process and results outcomes to MSF CoI
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation of INHERIT services: to align balancing technology with expectations from CH managers and further end users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One feedback workshop or event with MSF experts: Consolidating and sharing of key knowledge gained through both the INHERIT labs and the solution development process in view of improving and innovating CH management practices.
FURTHER ON DEMAND TO BE CO-DEFINED WITH THE MSF PARTICIPANTS	

The following table gives an overview and outlook on the major activities of the MSF.

Table 17: Major activities of the MSF

Activities	Month/s	Activitie/s	(Expected) Outcomes
MSF kick-off	M6	The official kick-off of the MSF with the participation of the WP leaders and followed by an engaging brainstorming session.	Clarified understanding among participants regarding the purpose and internal organisation of the MSF, as well as a defined structure for working groups and streamlined meeting logistics.
MSF agenda setting meeting	M8	WP leaders gathered to collectively shape the future agenda before implementation, ensuring alignment and clarity moving forward.	Cohesive future agenda, informed by the insights and strategic direction of the WP leaders.
Cross-fertilisation workshop	M10	Knowledge and experience sharing workshop after the completion of the first social lab events.	Reflect collectively on the outcomes and insights gained from the social lab kick-offs, learn from each other's experiences and best practices and develop further strategies for the upcoming social lab workshops.
INHERIT Info Desk	M14 – M18	A tool to provide guidance, assistance, and support to participants throughout the co-creation process.	Central point of contact for addressing questions, resolving issues, and ensuring smooth facilitation of the collaborative activities.
1 st forum with external stakeholders	Autumn 2024	The inaugural forum with external stakeholders providing a platform for diverse perspectives and strategic dialogue.	Foster mutual understanding, build networks for collaboration, and generate actionable insights to inform future decision-making and project implementation.

2 nd forum with external stakeholders	2025	Annual event with external stakeholders.	Fulfil dissemination of innovative INHERIT outcomes and approaches to the CH sector.
3 rd forum with external stakeholders	2026	Annual event with external stakeholders.	Maximise cooperation between INHERIT partners and key stakeholders.
4 th forum with external stakeholders	2027	Final event with external stakeholders in synergy with a conference.	Showcase project achievements, facilitate knowledge exchange and strengthen partnerships to ensure sustained impact beyond the project's conclusion.

Figure 24: Timeline of general activities in the MSF

4.3. Agenda Setting of the MSF

The MSF disseminates, exploits and further feedback the (interim) co-creation results of eight INHERIT social labs working. At the end of the project, the scenarios crafted in the labs are expected to be unique in their endorsement by various stakeholder groups.

One main attention is given to the role of CH for sustainable valorisation and retrofit and for a needs-based engagement of local communities. The second is on the enrolment of innovative problem solving and learning activities to strengthen the cultural heritage sector including its technical innovation potential through harnessing digital technologies, and for improving evidence-based

reporting on how CH operational management can benefit from proactively integrating good practices in social responsibility and values from the NEB in its day-to-day management⁴.

More granular topics and questions are expected to emerge during the project mirroring the participatory approach of co-creation.

Topics and questions are collected during the project process and during feedback formats with stakeholders and end users. The same applies to frequently asked questions, which are collected and answered through the INHERIT MSF Info Desk.

The following figure shows the interdependencies between the MSF, the INHERIT social labs, and the collaborative processes in INHERIT. The MSF acts at the intersection between project and process related co-design and the co-creation work in a real-world setting. It is possible that the INHERIT Social labs nominate representatives taking part in the MSF.

Figure 25: The interdependencies between the MSF and the INHERIT social labs

4.4. Building a Community of Interest

The definition of stakeholders and end users shall be also applied, when identifying potential MSF participants. Bringing together these types of stakeholders and the INHERIT project consortium, a community of interest can be built based on non-hierarchical partnerships among partners sharing their perspectives and expertise in mutual learning exercises.

⁴ Highlighted focal topics are linked to T2.1 and T2.3.

- A CoI can be described as a network of people, who share the same interests, overlapping or complementary knowledge, and an understanding of the best practices for subject matter related to the INHERIT project. A community of interest can be either a live “actual” community of individuals, who meet to discuss and exchange information, or it can be a virtual community that meets, discusses, and exchanges information via the Internet and various messaging tools.

All approaches intend to enhance the value creation process of INHERIT by including societal and social dimensions. Actors from science, technology and practice come together in the MSF to discuss and give feedback (while in the social labs it is to develop and test) for technologically and socially robust solutions based on a common understanding of the problem. The following groups have been identified in a collaborative brainstorming by INHERIT partners as relevant

- Core stakeholders from QH and key knowledge holders linked to the pilots
- Potential end users incl. representatives of future replication projects
- National and European networks of CH managers and cultural managers
- Sister projects in the Horizon framework and Interreg projects with overlapping topics or regions
- CH or environmental or social policy related representatives per region or at European level

The MSF set-up engages mixed stakeholder groups and end users with different vertical and horizontal influences as well as different needs and types of knowledge. In common is the expectation of a distinct engagement level of stakeholders, shared interest and expertise or knowledge in at least one of the objectives of the INHERIT project.

Hand in hand with the collaborative development of the agenda, the composition of stakeholders and the intensity of involvement can differ from topic to topic or phase to phase, respectively. Figure 26 shows the main aspects of the CoI such as the level of influence, acceptance, interest and connectivity.

Figure 26: The main aspects of the CoI

4.5. Benefits for participating Expert Stakeholders

The MSF provides a channel for advice, peer learning and networking. It serves as a platform for comprehensive discussions on these subjects, fostering collaboration and exploration of the INHERIT findings to address contemporary challenges. The forum invites e.g. cultural heritage and CCI practitioners, academic experts, (social) innovators, technology specialists, policy influencers as well decision takers or representatives from civil societies. These stakeholders can benefit by learning first-hand about INHERIT's process and findings and can raise questions or present their opinion. In this context, the concept involves a bundle of stakeholder groups with different vertical and horizontal influences as well as different types of knowledge and needs. In common is the expectation of a distinct engagement level of stakeholders and shared interest and expertise in at least one major objective of the INHERIT project.

4.6. General Layout and internal Organisation

The MSF serves as a central consultation platform between the MSF members and the different INHERIT boards which were created following a participatory leadership model. The leadership structure of the MSF Steering Board, or chair, is formed by the collective involvement of all WP leaders.

This collaborative approach ensures that the decision-making body reflects the diverse expertise and perspectives within the project. By bringing together leaders from each WP, this can lead effectively the direction of the MSF, guide discussions, set the agenda, and make informed decisions that align with the project's goals and objectives.

Moreover, the MSF is a modular consultation platform – as presented in the figure below – led by a board of INHERIT WP leaders and facilitated by the INHERIT Info Desk collecting questions, feedback and organising dedicated events of different scale.

In the thematic area boards, pilot leaders can discuss together their open questions on the process or results in the social labs whenever needed with external experts from the MSF stakeholder pool and use the critical friend method, which can be defined as a supportive person who can ask difficult questions using critical thinking. The INHERIT advisory board follows a common approach and invites academic and innovation experts at certain points of the project requesting their help to go beyond state of the art.

Figure 27: The MSF and its components

4.7. Regularity, Meeting Mode and Accessibility

The regularity of the MSF meetings will be structured to facilitate effective engagement with external stakeholders. Scheduled annually, these gatherings serve as key interfaces for collaboration and knowledge exchange. However, the frequency of engagements is adaptable, allowing for more frequent meetings based on demand. This flexible approach ensures that the MSF remains responsive to the needs and interests of its participants, allowing for timely discussions and actions to address emerging issues. With the active involvement of stakeholders, these meetings will serve as vital spaces for fostering partnerships, sharing insights, and driving progress towards shared goals.

The location of MSF meetings will be predominantly remote, leveraging digital platforms (e.g. Zoom, Microsoft Teams) to facilitate widespread participation and accessibility. This approach accommodates the diverse geographical locations of stakeholders and minimises logistical barriers. Embracing an inclusive approach, the stakeholder group will serve as an open forum, welcoming new attendees at any stage. This policy ensures that the MSF remains dynamic and responsive, continually evolving to incorporate diverse perspectives and expertise. By fostering an environment where participation is unrestricted, the forum can harness the collective wisdom and innovative ideas of a broad range of stakeholders.

Table 18: Implementation phases of the MSF

Phases / Activities	Description	(Expected) Outcomes
MSF kick-off M6	The official kick-off of the multi-stakeholder forum with the participation of the WP leaders and followed by an engaging brainstorming session.	Clarified understanding among participants regarding the purpose and internal organisation of the MSF, as well as a defined structure for working groups and streamlined meeting logistics.
MSF agenda setting meeting M8	WP leaders gathered to collectively shape the future agenda before implementation, ensuring alignment and clarity moving forward.	Cohesive future agenda, informed by the insights and strategic direction of the WP leaders.
INHERIT Info Desk M14	A tool to provide guidance, assistance, and support to participants throughout the co-creation process.	Central point of contact for addressing questions, resolving issues, and ensuring smooth facilitation of the collaborative activities.
1st Forum with external stakeholders Autumn 2024	The inaugural forum with external stakeholders providing a platform for diverse perspectives and strategic dialogue.	Foster mutual understanding, build networks for collaboration, and generate actionable insights to inform future decision-making and project implementation.
2 nd Forum with external stakeholders 2025	Annual event with external stakeholders.	Fulfil dissemination of innovative INHERIT outcomes and approaches to the CH sector.
3 rd Forum with external stakeholders 2026	Annual event with external stakeholders.	Maximise cooperation between INHERIT partners and key stakeholders.
4 th Forum with external stakeholders 2027	Final event with external stakeholders in synergy with a conference.	Showcase project achievements, facilitate knowledge exchange, and strengthen partnerships to ensure sustained impact beyond the project's conclusion.

5. Social Life Cycle Analyses

T2.2, also led by ZSI, approaches cultural heritage from the vantage point of social impact and sustainability. It undertakes a social lifecycle assessment of INHERIT's pilots, and more specifically of its cultural heritage management procedures and their governance. As literature shows, there is no ready-made methodology yet to conduct a S-LCA in the context of cultural heritage. The term S-LCA was originally coined by researching and studying the social impact of products and services across their lifecycle. According to the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2020), a S-LCA provides information on social aspects of products and services, including their potential positive and negative impacts along their whole life cycle, to provide more and better evidence for decision-making on related questions in this respect. UNEP developed guidelines on social lifecycle assessment for products and organisations based on which a generic S-LCA can be performed. These guidelines suggest a six-steps process, including

- the identification of processes and regions affected
- the identification of hotspots/prioritisation of social topics
- the relating risks to subcategories,
- the collecting data,
- the normalising data and
- visualising and interpreting of the results.

It is self-evident that CH buildings are by no means comparable with a product or service. In their management though, CH buildings take the form of organisations. Thus, the management of CH buildings entails quite similar aspects as the management of companies or public organisations. This is why knowledge transfer and the shadowing of methodological approaches from S-LCA of organisations to S-LCA of CH buildings is possible, in contrast to products or services.

While the lifecycle approach and the S-LCA have been discussed for the CH sector now for a longer time already (Settembre Blundo et al. 2014, Arcese et al. 2015), it seems what is at the core of S-LCA for organisations hasn't advanced into a widely established assessment framework for CH management until now. And this is where the INHERIT S-LCA comes in, as it focuses on the so called "triple bottom line" of organisational performance, including the levels of social, environmental, and economic performance. Through this lens we aim to observe, assess, and relatedly draw conclusions on how the INHERIT pilots are governed (institutional decision-making), based on which principles or guidelines (triple bottom line) and by whose involvement (inclusive or non-inclusive approach to involving stakeholders). Ultimately the results from the INHERIT S-LCA are aimed at charting new recommendations on how to move from S-LCA to pro-active S-LCM in the CH sector based on the triple bottom line of performance measuring.

The S-LCA is divided into **three assessment phases** aligned to the social lab process. The first assessment is conducted before the social lab kick-offs, the second in the middle of the running social lab activities and the third and last one after the social labs have ended. Assessments are done with semi-structured interviews at three points in the course of the co-creation process of INHERIT and one survey with owners, operators and decision-makers of each pilot building. A set of indicators has been developed, which is broad enough to respond to the specific context of each of the eight pilots. For indicator development, the bedrock has been two ISO standards – one on the technical (ISO 14040) and one on the social (ISO 26000) dimension of CH management. The analysis of these two standards was further extended with relevant literature, mainly on the topics of energy and social inclusion, CH operation/governance and social inclusion and cooperation between cultural heritage and the third sector on social inclusion.

The visualisation below indicates this development process for the INHERIT S-LCA indicators and the main sources used for it.

Figure 28: S-LCA indicators and its resources

Social labs and the S-LCA should be regarded as two activities running in parallel. Both are aimed at fostering the knowledge about social and technical innovations in the management of cultural heritage buildings and to provide practical skills to those concerned with management about their implementation in site-specific contexts. The following main difference is important to note though: While the aim of the social labs is to instigate a real transition in the approach to cultural heritage management on the ground, taking into account INHERIT's principles of technical modernisation and social innovation, the S-LCA will – on a level beyond the actual workshop participants – monitor how the knowledge generated in these workshops is integrated into the personal and institutional culture, particularly in how aspects of social inclusion (innovation) are addressed at these levels.

Table 19: Implementation phases of the S-LCA

Phases Sequences	Months	Activities	(Expected) Outcomes
Literature analysis (incl. ISO), Desk research, key stakeholder identification	M3 – M5	ZSI conducted an in-depth literature analysis about societal and social responsibility dimension in CH management and retrieved first set of potential indicators from two ISO standards; Pilot partners identified key stakeholders with relevance to S-LCA	Literature stock, pool of potential indicators and eight different stakeholders overviews
Concept note preparation	M5	ZSI drafted a concept note based on the process in phase 1; the concept note was co-designed with pilot partners and selected partners from other WPs whose activities overlap with S-LCA through feedback loops;	Final concept note as a jointly agreed working document between consortium partners outlining the S-LCA process for the project
Internal preparatory workshop	M5	Detailed presentation of a concept note, discussion of steps and roles involved in implementing the S-LCA at the eight pilot sites; workshop was done in train-the-trainers format to create co-ownership at pilots' side for the S-LCA activity	Giving a signal to pilot partners that the S-LCA activity is launched;
Selection of S-LCA indicators and questionnaire	M6	Based on the outcomes of phases 1-3 and one more consultative meeting between ZSI and WP5 partners (who were working on indicators for technical monitoring as well), the final selection of indicators was done; Drawing on these indicators, a questionnaire for the 1 st assessment was drafted.	Final set of indicators for socially inclusive, responsible and innovative CH management; Interview questionnaire for 1 st S-LCA assessment
1 st S-LCA	M7 – M10	8 pilot partners conduct first round of interviews (at least 4) with owners, operators and decision-makers of their buildings	Min. of 32 interviews conducted based on which the first baseline assessment is done

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2 nd S-LCA	M20 – M21 8 pilot partners conduct second round of interviews (at least 4) with owners, operators and decision-makers of their buildings; interview questions refined based on learnings from 1 st assessment	Min. of 32 interviews conducted based on which the mid-term assessment is done
3 rd S-LCA	M34 – M37 8 pilot partners conduct second round of interviews (at least 4) with owners, operators and decision-makers of their buildings; Interview questions refined based on learnings from 2 nd assessment	Min. of 32 interviews conducted based on which the final assessment is done
Final comparative analysis and report	M38 – M40 Final comparative analysis of the three S-LCA assessments preparing for the final S-LCA report	Final results from S-LCA and report on social impact of INHERIT pilots

6. Co-Creation of the INHERIT Services

As already highlighted, co-creation as a method attains a central role in the INHERIT project. Social labs are a recognised scientific method to organise co-creative engagement processes aimed at co-producing joint outputs between traditional “owners” of knowledge/expertise or services/products and selected stakeholders assigned to becoming involved in this process.

INHERIT’s technical services, offering next generation solutions for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient and resilient cultural heritage based on a new ICT-based platform (which, itself, is built with comprehensive data collected from all pilots by digital means, e.g. Digital Twins, H-BIM etc.), will become a key legacy of the project, extending the project’s official runtime. To make them attractive and interesting to end users of diverse backgrounds. This includes for example **commercial end users such as architects, engineers etc. who are interested in using INHERIT’s solutions for own work OR non-commercial end users**, such as residents or owners of the building, who are interested that the site-specific solution is tailor-made to the local context by reflecting their ideas and needs. It is critical to involve various representatives of these end user groups from the very beginning of this process. This chapter describes **how INHERIT approaches the involvement and engagement of end users in the development of technical services against the highlighted background of co-creation**. It provides details how the technical service development is embedded in the established social labs and how the development will progress along three main phases of action.

In the first phase of this task started (M4-M12) information, and feedback about the INHERIT services will be collected by the INHERIT stakeholders and to understand the needs of the different pilots and how these services can be best integrated to the CH sites.

At the time of writing this deliverable, a series of meetings with pilots and service providers were conducted, based on which the user story template (to collect user scenarios, see illustration) and the service description template (to collect service descriptions, see illustration) was developed. This process resulted in the collection of 28 user stories and related service descriptions.

6.1. Collection of User Stories – 1st Phase

The focus of this phase is on collecting information and feedback about the INHERIT services from end users and on understanding the needs of the different pilots in view of integrating the future services in the site-specific CH buildings. For this reason, **a co-creation workshop was held online in M8, involving both the eight INHERIT pilots and end user representing various sectors with relevance to CH**. A total of 44 people attended the workshop (out of which 56% were female and 44% were male participants), coming from different European countries. Researchers, application developers, engineers, and architects, among others, brainstormed around the services of the INHERIT project. Their valuable feedback regarding the user requirements will assist in consolidating

the final version of the user requirements that will enhance the development of the services. It is noteworthy that the participants shared their thoughts, not only on the strengths and opportunities but also on the weaknesses and threats that will prevent us from potential barriers along the way.

The documentation of this workshop was made accessible through a whiteboard, which was jointly developed by the workshop participants. Below two snapshots of the results documentation are provided.

Figure 29: Documentation of 1st co-creation workshop to technical solution development in INHERIT: Example of finding solutions for IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation

Figure 30: Snapshot from Miro on documentation of first co-creation workshop to technical solution development in INHERIT: drivers and barriers in service development

Moreover, two templates were created – one targeting the pilot leaders (user story template) and one targeting the potential service providers (service description template). In this context, service providers are the technical partners in the INHERIT consortium developing the designated services. This process resulted in the collection of 28 user stories and related service descriptions.

The collection of user stories with the help of the user story template by all pilot partners led to the following overview.

Table 20: Collection of user stories

	U.S No	U.S Title
Pilot 1	US 1.1	Sensors and monitoring system
	US 1.2	Optimal renovation strategies
	US 1.3	Measured and quantified thermal comfort and air quality
	US 1.4	Energy performance analysis
	US 1.5	KPIs impacted by different climate scenarios
Pilot 2	US 2.1	Simulating our energy consumptions and expected expenses
	US 2.2	Simulating our energy consumptions and expected expenses
Pilot 3	US 3.1	Operational recommendations for noise comfort and air quality
	US 3.2	Energy performance analysis
	US 3.3	Operational recommendations for crowd and mobility management
	US 3.4	Optimal renovation planning proposals based on energy performance data
Pilot 4	US 4.1	Visualisation of energy performance of the building
	US 4.2	Renovation action plan
	US 4.3	Regulated indoor air quality
	US 4.4	Clustered with other CH buildings
Pilot 5	US 5.1	Sensor and monitoring system for building maintenance
	US 5.2	Selection of the optimal renovation scenario based on energy performance data and AR/VR interface
Pilot 6	US 6.1	Checking the feasibility of preventive conservation and proper maintenance of CH buildings with HBIM and its cost-effective energy performance optimisation.
	US 6.2	Recommendation on Historic Urban Landscape for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation and preservation of the CH building
Pilot 7	US 7.1	Modelling and simulation environment
	US 7.2	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management

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	US 7.3	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance
	US 7.4	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios
Pilot 8	US 8.1	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios
	US 8.2	Collecting data related to energy performance
	US 8.3	Assessment of optimal renovation approaches
	US 8.4	Enhancement of crowd and mobility management
	US 8.5	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios

The next steps were to map the user stories to the stakeholders, which were already identified for the social lab process and then to extract and analyse the user requirements based on the meta-information collected for the user stories (see table below).

Then the **co-creation workshop** was organised. Its main goal was to receive feedback on the user requirements identified internally through brainstorming sessions and interactive activities between the pilot partners and end users.

Table 21: User stories: further contextualisation

	US No	U.S Title	End User / Stakeholders		
			High Importance	Medium Importance	Low Importance
Pilot 1 REGEA	US 1.1	Sensors and monitoring system	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County
	US 1.2	Optimal renovation strategies	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection	Community of Cultural Associations of City of Jastrebarsko	City of Jastrebarsko
	US 1.3	Measured and quantified thermal comfort and air quality	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Croatian Forest Research Institute
	US 1.4	Energy performance analysis	Faculty of Civil Engineering at University of Zagreb	Public Institution Green Ring of Zagreb County	Administrative Department for Spatial Planning, Construction and Environmental Protection

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	US 1.5	KPIs impacted by different climate scenarios	Conservation Department of Ministry for Culture and Media for the Area of Zagreb County	Administrative Department for Culture, Sport, Technical Culture and Civil Society of Zagreb County	City of Jastrebarsko
Pilot 2 BOUYGUE	US 2.1	Simulating our energy consumptions and expected expenses	Tenant	Architects	Centre Pompidou
	US 2.2	Simulating our energy consumptions and expected expenses	Tenant	Architects	Centre Pompidou
Pilot 3 ELLET	US 3.1	Operational recommendations for noise comfort and air quality	Municipality of Athens – Deputy Mayor of Athens	Architectural Council of Licensing	Committee of Plaka Residents' Initiative
	US 3.2	Energy performance analysis	NEB committee – Ministry of Energy	Students, researchers (National Technical University of Athens)	Engineers (volunteers)
	US 3.3	Operational recommendations for crowd and mobility management	Technical Chamber of Greece	Greek Association of Architects	Students and researchers (National Technical University of Athens)
	US 3.4	Optimal renovation planning proposals based on energy performance data	Architectural Council for Licensing	Greek Historic Houses Project	Local Association of Athens
Pilot 4 RPR	US 4.1	Visualisation of energy performance of the building	Riga Energy Agency	Technology provider	Riga Technical University
	US 4.2	Renovation action plan	Riga City Council (Construction Authority)	Disabled people (NGO Sustento)	Riga City Council (Financial department)
	US 4.3	Regulated indoor air quality	Riga City Council (Construction Authority)	Riga Technical University	Financial Institution (Latvian Environmental Investment Fund)
	US 4.4	Clustered with other CH buildings	Riga City Council (Property Department)	AVE SOL building users - choirs	National Cultural Heritage Administration
Pilot 5 FASADA	US 5.1	Sensor and monitoring system for building maintenance	3L Architekten	Department of Regional and Spatial Development	energy department of city of Gdynia

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	US 5.2	Selection of the optimal renovation scenario based on energy performance data and AR/VR interface	Energy Department of City of Gdynia	Pich architects	Mostostal Warszawa S.A. - Construction
Pilot 6 CARTIF	US 6.1	Checking the feasibility of preventive conservation and proper maintenance of CH buildings with H-BIM and its cost-effective energy performance optimisation.	Direccion General de Patrimonio Cultural. Consejeria de Cultura; Turismo y Deporte. jcyL	Consejeria de Cultura, Turismo y Deporte. jcyL	AEICE
	US 6.2	Recommendation on Historic Urban Landscape for cost-effective and less disruptive modernisation and preservation of the CH building	Consejeria de Cultura, Turismo y Deporte. jcyL	Direccion General de Patrimonio Cultural. Consejeria de Cultura; Turismo y Deporte. jcyL	AEICE
Pilot 7 UU	US 7.1	Modelling and simulation environment	Byggnadsvårds företagen	Riksantikvarie ämbetet	Byggnadsvårdsföretagen
	US 7.2	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	Energicentrum gotland	Riksantikvarie ämbetet	House owners in Visby/Fatighetsägarna gotland
	US 7.3	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Byggnadsvårds företagen	House owners in Visby/Fatighetsägarna gotland	Riksantikvarie ämbetet
	US 7.4	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	Visby innerstadsförening	Världsarv Srådet	House owners in Visby/fatighetsägarna gotland
Pilot 8 IBB	US 8.1	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios	Academic Scholars using the Archive Building	Yaşar University, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National Library Foundation
	US 8.2	Collecting data related to energy performance		Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National Library Foundation
	US 8.3	Assessment of optimal renovation approaches	Department of City Planning Supervision	Constructor	Izmir first Conservation Council of Cultural Heritage
	US 8.4	Enhancement of crowd and mobility management	Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir first Conservation Council of Cultural Heritage	Directorate of City Archive, Museums and Libraries

	US 8.5	Assessing impacts of different climate scenarios	Academic Scholars using the Archive Building	Yaşar University, Izmir, Türkiye	Izmir National library foundation
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The full process for the first phase of the technical service development is visualised in the figure below.

Figure 31: First phase workflow: co-design of technical solutions

6.2. Co-design of user-friendly Environments: 2nd Phase

In the second phase, starting with M12, the co-design of user-friendly environments and the user flow diagrams will be conducted. An additional online workshop is planned for this period to receive further feedback on the interaction of the end users with the services. Service providers may also conduct additional workshops/sessions to involve both technical stakeholders and other end users, such as site visitors and facility managers, during the design of service UI.

6.3. Refinement of Usability: 3rd Phase

In the third and final phase, starting in M23, the demo versions of the proposed service solutions will be available for stakeholders to test. Additionally, a short assessment will be developed to refine the tools and their usability to the end users. This will help in improving the tools and in providing a more user-friendly experience, while contributing to the multi-dimensional evaluation of the services during the pilot activities.

The workshops in phases 2 and 3 can already benefit from the social lab process, which has been kicked off and further consolidated in the first eight months of the project. In contrary to the first

co-creation workshop on technical solutions development from M8, when the first social lab workshops of the eight pilot partners were only about to start (in fact, the eight social lab workshops were kicked off in a timeframe between end of M8 and beginning of M10), forthcoming workshops are supposed to utilise the by-then-established social lab process where needed. In practical terms this means that the technical oriented workshops could be integrated as part of one or more of the forthcoming social lab workshops to facilitate the participation of locally embedded end users, both of professional/commercial and non-commercial background. Linking these two types of co-creation workshops in a physical (alternatively in a hybrid) setting will allow for a high number of participants and a high intensity of engagement, catering to the successful realisation of a user-centric journey in technical solution development for the cultural heritage sector.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

Regarding the activities already concluded, still ongoing or at future horizon, one can distinguish between co-design of approaches with the internal consortium partners and co-creation activities with the external stakeholders – both are iterative processes. In any case, co-design activities with partners from the INHERIT consortium were implemented as a pre-requisite to realise the co-creation process, which builds upon them.

The **engagement** and **co-creation strategy**, which enables the development of **eight stakeholder mappings** and generates a stakeholder pool in form of a living document. This is an important pillar for the stakeholder recruitment and the practical co-creation work between the pilot partners and the stakeholders from QH in the **social labs**. Research and co-creation activities also bridge the social labs with the **MSF**, which are both the two major engagement instruments addressing and involving **800 stakeholders** via collaborative activities and specific communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts.

This number is expected to be reached through the variety of co-creation activities in INHERIT including those with a social or a management or a technical scope. The reach-out to and the involvement of the stakeholders with previously predefined engagement levels (from informing at level 1 to the collaboration with potential end-users at level 5) will feed during the project duration into a pool of stakeholders at local (or pilot) and at European level.

Other key components are the **S-LCA** assessing the INHERIT transition, the **NEB values** as a framework for change and the **technically oriented co-creation process** with potential end-users as the main target group for the **service solutions** developed.

Examples of activities now in full swing to render more detailed and improved versions of outcomes in the forthcoming months are the final conceptualisation of the MSF (including the composition of stakeholders invited and the range of topics of the MSF events to be organised), the continuous adaption of the S-LCA questionnaire based on the feedbacks received by pilot partners who have already carried out their interviews with **OODs**, the capacity building measures to transmit knowledge about NEB values to the pilots and the service solution description based on the co-design journey with technical end users.

Against this background, the following outlook on next activities can be made at this stage (M8) to sketch future outcomes, which will be analysed in follow-up reports.

- **Enhancing social accessibility and inclusiveness in CH sites** (start date M14): This task will ensure that social accessibility and inclusiveness for CH sites are promoted to the pilots. This is done as part of the social labs and in parallel to WP5 activities.

- **Continuous dialogue and support for MSF** (start state M14): This task supervises the MSF until the end of the project. The MSF Info Desk is established as part of the project website and catering to the needs of MSF participants and other interested parties with most important information and FAQs. The first step is implemented with the launch of an online landing page integrated into the INHERIT project website.
- **Active societal participation and enabling conditions for the INHERIT heritage-built environment** (due in M18): This deliverable reports about measures implemented to diffuse and foster knowledge about active societal participation and enabling conditions for the built CH environment across the eight INHERIT pilots.

All major activities from M1 to M10 are made visible on the following timeline.

Figure 32: Timeline of the overall co-creation processes in WP2

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9. Appendix

9.1. Interdependencies of Tasks in WP2 of INHERIT

LEGEND:

- T2.1.1 → Fostering CH eco-systems linked to INHERIT pilots (M1-6)
- T2.1.2 → Establishment of the INHERIT Social Labs (M4-39)
- T2.3 → Social engagement, values and working principles for the INHERIT heritage-built environment (M3-39)
- T2.3.1 → Fostering the New European Bauhaus values and working principles (M3-14)
- T2.3.2 → Enhancing social accessibility and inclusiveness in CH sites (M14-37)
- T2.4 → Co-creating the INHERIT solutions and user scenarios (M4-29)
- WP3 → Framework for assessment and monitoring of CH, and catalogue of solutions towards sustainability and resource-efficiency (M3-34)
- WP4 → Decision support services for the heritage-built environment's life cycle (M4-36)
- WP5 → Demonstration of INHERIT towards sustainable and resilient CH (M1-40)
- T5.1 → Implementation plans and continuous tracking (M1-13)
- T5.2 → Continuous dialogue and support for Multi-stakeholder Forum (M14-40)
- WP6 → INHERIT capacity building, policy support and standardisation (M1-42)

9.2. List of transregional and European Stakeholders

ORGANISATIONS	AIM	CONTEXT TO INHERIT PROJECT	DOCUMENTS/POLICIES OF IMPORTANCE FOR INHERIT
<u>THE ASSOCIATION OF CULTURAL ENCOUNTER CENTRES (ACCR)</u>	The Association of Cultural Encounter Centres (ACCR) aims to promote a contemporary view of heritage and creativity which is in harmony with modern society and contributes to the development of innovation, sustainability and inclusiveness within its territories.	The Association of Cultural Encounter Centres (ACCR) connects heritage sites with artistic, cultural, and scientific initiatives, promoting cultural heritage preservation. By facilitating intercultural dialogue and residency programs for artists and culture professionals, the ACCR strengthens the local and global impact of cultural heritage sites, supported by the French Ministry of Culture.	There were no publications found from The Association of Cultural Encounter Centres (ACCR).
<u>EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE RESTORATION COMPANIES (AEERPA)</u>	European Association of Architectural Heritage Restoration Companies (AEERPA) aims to defend the interests of architectural heritage restoration companies and emphasises the importance of conservation and restoration to safeguard the future of cultural heritage.	AEERPA unites restoration companies across Europe to maintain and enhance the skills and craftsmanship necessary for the conservation and restoration of architectural heritage. The association advocates for the importance of quality restoration work to preserve the cultural value of heritage sites and promotes sustainable development through heritage conservation efforts.	There were no publications found from European Association of Architectural Heritage Restoration Companies (AEERPA).
<u>THE BLUE SHIELD</u>	The Blue Shield is committed to the protection of the world's cultural property and is concerned with the protection of cultural and natural heritage, tangible and intangible.	The Blue Shield operates under the principles established by the 1954 Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property. This organisation works globally to safeguard museums, archives, libraries, monuments, and heritage sites from the detrimental effects of war and natural disasters.	<u>A four-tier approach to the protection of cultural property in the event of armed conflict.</u>

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<u>EUROPEAN CONFEDERATION OF CONSERVATOR-RESTORERS' ORGANISATIONS (E.C.C.O.)</u>	<p>European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers' Organisations (E.C.C.O.) aims to develop and promote, on a practical, scientific and cultural level, the profession of Conservator-Restorer of Cultural Property.</p>	<p>E.C.C.O. promotes the conservation and restoration profession by developing and maintaining high professional standards, advocating for legal recognition, and fostering education and training for conservator-restorers.</p>	<p><u>FOSTERING INNOVATION IN HERITAGE PROFESSIONS: THE EFFECT OF THE EYCH</u></p>
<u>EUROPEAN CULTURAL FOUNDATION (ECF)</u>	<p>European Cultural Foundation (ECF) aims to share knowledge across the cultural sector, and to campaign for the arts at all levels of political decision-making.</p>	<p>The foundation advocates for integrating culture into the core of EU policies and initiatives, recognising its role in shaping a resilient and sustainable future for Europe. ECF's initiatives, such as the Cultural Deal for Europe, aim to include cultural heritage in strategic EU programs, policies, and financial mechanisms.</p>	<p><u>POLICY ANALYSIS, POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS</u></p>
<u>EUROPEAN COUNCIL FOR THE VILLAGE AND SMALL TOWN (ECOVAST)</u>	<p>European Council for the Village and Small Town (ECOVAST) aims to foster the economic, social and cultural vitality and the administrative identity of rural communities throughout Europe.</p>	<p>ECOVAST activities focus on fostering the economic, social, and cultural vitality of rural areas, while promoting the renewal of their built and natural environments. It acts as a bridge between local actors and policymakers, offering a platform for the exchange of best practices and ideas related to rural development and heritage conservation.</p>	<p><u>The Importance of Small Towns published by ECOVAST November 2014</u></p>
<u>EUROPEAN CULTURAL TOURISM NETWORK (ECTN)</u>	<p>European Cultural Tourism Network (ECTN) aims to bring together the tourism and cultural industry professionals working in different regions of Europe to exchange experience and information on best practice and to develop new approaches and innovations.</p>	<p>ECTN facilitates collaboration among tourism and cultural industry professionals, aiming to enhance cultural tourism's role in sustainable development and the preservation of cultural assets.</p>	<p>There were no publications found from European Cultural Tourism Network (ECTN).</p>

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EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF FORTIFIED SITES (EFFORTS)	<p>European Federation of Fortified Sites (EFFORTS) aims to establish a permanent European network of fortified heritage sites, to support the set-up of international partnerships between cities and sites, experts, policy makers, enterprises and practitioners and join members in the development of fortification heritage.</p>	<p>The European Federation of Fortified Sites (EFFORTS) is a beacon in the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage, specifically focusing on fortified sites that bear historical significance across Europe.</p>	<p>The European Union peer-learning scheme on cultural heritage for cities and regions</p>
EUROPEAN NETWORK OF CULTURAL ADMINISTRATION TRAINING CENTRES (ENCATC)	<p>European Network of Cultural Administration Training Centres (ENCATC) is a European network gathering higher educational institutions and training organisations dealing with cultural management education and training.</p>	<p>The European Network of Cultural Administration Training Centres (ENCATC) serves as a link to the realm of cultural heritage by nurturing a network of educational institutions dedicated to training future cultural administrators.</p>	<p>Policy paper: ENCATC applauds the new EU guidelines for the cultural sector</p>
EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR CONSERVATION-RESTORATION EDUCATION (ENCoRE)	<p>European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education (ENCoRE) promotes research and education in the field of conservation and restoration of cultural heritage.</p>	<p>The European Network for Conservation-Restoration Education (ENCoRE) plays a pivotal role in the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage through its focus on conservation and restoration education. By linking institutions and professionals dedicated to this field, ENCoRE fosters collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the development of best practices.</p>	<p>Towards an EU Strategy for Cultural Heritage –The Case for Research</p>

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<u>THE EUROPEAN ROUTE OF INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE (ERIH)</u>	<p>ERIH – The European Route of Industrial Heritage (ERIH) raises overall awareness of our common European industrial heritage; encourage the exchange of experience; strengthen European cooperation; attract new audiences, develop new formats for events and increase appreciation of Industrial Heritage as an important aspect of cultural heritage.</p>	<p>Through collaborations with local communities, governments, and cultural organizations, ERIH supports the conservation, interpretation, and sustainable development of industrial heritage sites. ERIH's efforts contribute to heritage tourism, educational programs, and research initiatives, fostering greater awareness and appreciation of Europe's industrial legacy.</p>	<p>There were no publications found from The European Route of Industrial Heritage (ERIH).</p>
<u>EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF HISTORY EDUCATORS (EUROCLIO)</u>	<p>European Association of History Educators (EUROCLIO) supports the development of responsible and innovative history, citizenship and heritage education by promoting critical thinking, multi-perspectivity, mutual respect, and the inclusion of controversial issues.</p>	<p>Through collaborative projects and partnerships with museums, archives, and cultural institutions, EUROCLIO promotes active learning and engagement with cultural heritage among students and educators. The association advocates for the integration of cultural heritage education into national and international education policies to ensure its continued relevance and significance in history education.</p>	<p><u>Innovating History Education for All Needs Assessment</u></p>
<u>THE VOICE OF CULTURAL HERITAGE IN EUROPE (EUROPA NOSTRA)</u>	<p>The Voice of Cultural Heritage in Europe (EUROPA NOSTRA) is a rapidly growing citizens' movement for the safeguarding of Europe's cultural and natural heritage.</p>	<p>EUROPA NOSTRA serves as the authoritative voice for cultural heritage in Europe, advocating for its preservation and promoting public awareness. Through its initiatives and partnerships, EUROPA NOSTRA works to safeguard Europe's diverse heritage for future generations.</p>	<p><u>Putting Europe's shared heritage at the heart of the European Green Deal</u></p>
<u>EUROPEANA</u>	<p>Europeana is Europe's platform for digital cultural heritage, empowering cultural heritage institutions to share their collections with the world.</p>	<p>Europeana is a digital platform that provides access to millions of cultural heritage items from European museums, galleries, libraries, and archives. It serves as a gateway to Europe's cultural treasures, offering users the opportunity to explore and engage with diverse artifacts and collections online.</p>	<p>There were no publications found from Europeana.</p>

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INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL ON MONUMENTS AND SITES (ICOMOS)	<p>International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS) aims to promote the application of theory, methodology, and scientific techniques to the conservation of the architectural and archaeological heritage.</p>	<p>ICOMOS is a global organisation dedicated to the conservation and protection of cultural heritage sites worldwide. Through research, advocacy, and expertise, ICOMOS plays a key role in preserving the world's architectural, archaeological, and cultural treasures for future generations.</p>	<p>Heritage and the sustainable development goals: policy guidance for heritage and development actors</p>
INTERNATIONAL NATIONAL TRUSTS ORGANISATION (INTO)	<p>International National Trusts Organisation (INTO) aims to develop and promote best conservation practices, increase the capacity of individual organizations, establish Trusts where they do not presently exist, and advocate in the interests of heritage conservation.</p>	<p>The International National Trusts Organization (INTO) is a global network that connects National Trust organizations from around the world. INTO fosters collaboration, knowledge exchange, and advocacy for the preservation and stewardship of natural and cultural heritage sites by National Trusts worldwide.</p>	<p>FROM START- UP to SUSTAINABILITY</p>
SOUTHEAST EUROPEAN HERITAGE NETWORK (SEE HERITAGE NETWORK)	<p>Southeast European Heritage Network (SEE Heritage Network) aims to protect and promote the common cultural heritage with the goal of encouraging sustainable development of the region.</p>	<p>The Southeast European Heritage Network (SEE Heritage Network) is a collaborative platform dedicated to preserving and promoting cultural heritage in Southeast Europe. Through partnerships and shared resources, SEE Heritage Network strengthens efforts to safeguard the diverse cultural heritage of the region for future generations.</p>	<p>Towards a performative turn in heritage studies</p>
TRANS EUROPE HALLES (TEH)	<p>Trans Europe Halles (TEH) aims to strengthen the sustainable development of non-governmental cultural centres and encourage new initiatives by connecting, supporting and promoting them and to connect all players who are engaged in transforming spaces into cultural</p>	<p>Trans Europe Halles (TEH) is a network of cultural centers across Europe, repurposing historic buildings and industrial spaces for contemporary cultural use. By revitalising these sites, TEH fosters cultural innovation, community engagement, and the preservation of Europe's architectural heritage.</p>	<p>TEH: Building a Cultural Regeneration Project for Europe</p>

	centres to the benefit of their communities.		
RÉSEAU ART NOUVEAU NETWORK (RANN)	Réseau Art Nouveau Network (RANN) aims to keep professionals informed and to make the general public aware of the cultural significance and European dimension of this heritage on our very own doorstep.	Réseau Art Nouveau Network (RANN) is a collaborative network dedicated to the preservation and promotion of Art Nouveau heritage across Europe. Through research, advocacy, and cultural exchange, RANN works to raise awareness and safeguard the architectural and artistic legacy of the Art Nouveau movement for future generations.	Art Nouveau & ecology
ASSOCIATION OF HISTORIC THEATRES IN EUROPE (PERSPECTIV)	Association of Historic Theatres in Europe (PERSPECTIV) encourage and support the conservation and restoration of historic theatres, secure the continuous exchange between these theatres and everybody interested in them and initiate and support research.	The Association of Historic Theatres in Europe (PERSPECTIV) is a network devoted to the preservation and promotion of Europe's historic theatre buildings. PERSPECTIV facilitates collaboration among theatre professionals and heritage experts to ensure the continued relevance and appreciation of these cultural landmarks.	There were no publications found from Association of Historic Theatres in Europe (PERSPECTIV).
EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR HERITAGE INTERPRETATION (INTERPRET EUROPE)	European Association for Heritage Interpretation (INTERPRET EUROPE) encourages dialogue and partnerships between associations and universities, providers and professionals from more than 40 countries to share their expertise in making heritage more meaningful to people.	Interpret Europe serves as the leading European association dedicated to promoting heritage interpretation. Through training, advocacy, and collaboration, Interpret Europe enhances the understanding and appreciation of cultural heritage by engaging audiences in meaningful and interactive experiences.	Third space in culture, heritage and learning
ORGANIZATION OF WORLD HERITAGE CITIES (OWHC)	Organization of World Heritage Cities (OWHC) aims to favor the implementation of the World Heritage Convention, to encourage co-operation and the exchange of information and	The Organization of World Heritage Cities (OWHC) is a global network committed to the preservation and promotion of urban cultural heritage. OWHC facilitates exchange and cooperation among its member cities, fostering sustainable	Cultural Tourism & Visitor Management Framework

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	<p>expertise on matters of conservation and management as well as to develop a sense of solidarity among its member cities.</p>	<p>management practices to safeguard their rich cultural legacies.</p>	
<p><u>NETWORK OF EUROPEAN REGIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE AND COMPETITIVE TOURISM (NECSTOUR)</u></p>	<p>Network of European Regions for a Sustainable and Competitive Tourism (NECSTOUR) brings together around 38 regions of Europe with a strong competency in tourism, as well as tourism-related academic organisations such as universities and research institutes, and representatives of sustainable and responsible tourism business associations and networks from around 20 Member States.</p>	<p>NECSTOUR, the Network of European Regions for Sustainable and Competitive Tourism, emphasises the role of cultural heritage in promoting sustainable tourism development. By fostering collaboration among regions, NECSTOUR works to leverage cultural heritage assets for economic growth while ensuring their preservation and responsible management.</p>	<p><u>NECSTOUR Climate Action Plan</u></p>
<p><u>MICHAEL CULTURE ASSOCIATION (MCA)</u></p>	<p>Michael Culture Association (MCA) aims to promote and valorise European cultural heritage through digitisation and dissemination to a European and worldwide audience and to enhance the network of European professionals working on cultural and digital cultural heritage (DCH).</p>	<p>The Michael Culture Association (MCA) is dedicated to advancing digital cultural heritage initiatives across Europe. Through collaborative projects and knowledge sharing, MCA facilitates the preservation, accessibility, and promotion of Europe's cultural heritage in the digital age.</p>	<p>There were no publications found from Michael Culture Association (MCA).</p>
<p><u>THE EUROPEAN HISTORIC HOUSES ASSOCIATION (EHHA)</u></p>	<p>The European Historic Houses Association (EHHA) serves as a platform for collaboration and knowledge exchange among historic house owners, professionals, and policymakers. EHHA</p>	<p>The European Historic Houses Association (EHHA) serves as a key link to cultural heritage by advocating for the preservation and promotion of historic houses across Europe. Through collaboration and advocacy, EHHA works to</p>	<p>There were no publications found from The European Historic Houses Association (EHHA).</p>

also works to raise awareness about the cultural, economic, and social contributions of historic houses to European heritage and society.

ensure that these architectural treasures continue to enrich Europe's cultural landscape for future generations.

9.3. Co-Design Process MSF

MSF Kick-off: MENTIMETER 1 RESULTS (26/03/24)

Participants: ZSI, SLG, ICONS, ICLEI, CARTIF, ICCS

MSF RATIONALE:	Agreed	Comments
<p>The INHERIT Multi-Stakeholder Forum (MSF) aims to enhance open and accountable decision-making as well as good governance of INHERIT interventions through the continuous engagement of stakeholders in these forums, and in the action that flows from their work. Furthermore, the MSF provides a channel for advice and peer learning between researchers, technology innovators and practitioners from management.</p> <p>INHERIT's innovative practices and technologies contribute to gaining leadership in creative climate change mitigation solutions based on energy efficiency tools and a sustainable valorisation strategy of cultural heritage. Furthermore, INHERIT'S strategy and scope encompasses principles of social responsibility and values of the New European Bauhaus. To assure the adaption and uptake of innovation, INHERIT fosters social lifecycle practices in the context of cultural heritage management, which is understood as a green and socially inclusive managerial practices and performance.</p>	✓	It would be good to specify the relation of MSF to Social Labs.

MSF PURPOSES:	Agreed	Comments
To enable innovation partnerships by connecting key stakeholders from the INHERIT Labs and the MSF.	✓	Students, entrepreneurs, future projects...
To create a transdisciplinary expert group from research, innovation, and practice	✓	1)MSF could be more oriented on the pilots or potential replicators and do not represent an expert group per se. 2) Perhaps we should go more beyond academia.
Align balancing technology with expectations from CH managers and further end users	50% ✓	-
To collaborate with HORIZON sister projects	✓	Yes, if it is relevant for MSF purposes.
To build a community of interest (a community of interest is a gathering of people assembled around a topic of common interest).	✓	What is the topic for community of interest for INHERIT?

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To find a connection between groups that would normally do not collaborate.	✓	-
To empower minority perspectives in the MSF	✓	-
To allow on a transregional scale knowledge sharing and cooperation opportunities, both, in the co-design and the application of socially inclusive technical services for cultural heritage based on the solutions developed in INHERIT.	✓	-
To raise awareness and sensitivity towards important issues with certain groups/individuals.	✓	-
To maximise participation and cooperation and to create a safe space for sharing	✓	-
Do you expect further remits, how MSF can contribute to your organisational or project success?	✓	-

MSF AGENDA SETTING:	Agreed	Comments
Topics discussed in the MSF shall include i.e. CH and retrofit, green technologies, social innovation/social inclusion, NEB values	✓	The four pillars of the INHERIT project as defined in the GA?
Which topic shall be excluded and discussed in another context?	-	-

MSF INTERNAL ORGANISATION: The MSF Steering Board (or chair) includes:	Agreed	Comments
all WP-Leaders	✓	1)Specify the role and duties of the MSF. 2) ZSI as task leader could be the "Steering Committee". WPL could be asked to gather feedback, needs and topics for the events... but not for organisational aspects. 3) AB members- as an additional option, we can also update the AB about the MSF and get feedback.
SLG and another partner to be defined		

MSF ACCESSIBILITIES:	Agreed	Comments
The stakeholder group will be an open forum for new attendees to join at any point. Do you agree?	✓	Depending on the topics already covered (before new ones joined and the follow-up of the meetings)
MSF REGULARITY:	Agreed	
Steering board and thematic area boards quarterly a year with more frequent engagement based on demand		
Interface with external stakeholders yearly with more frequent engagement based on demand		✓
MSF LOCATION:	Agreed	
In general, remote. Do you agree?		✓
SUGGESTION TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MSF: Do you agree?	Agreed	
<p>1st PHASE: DEFINITION M6-7</p> <p>Incl. co-design of the MSF, Information & guidance document, term of reference, online registration for MSF members (i.e. online survey with informed consent)</p> <p>2nd PHASE: BUILD M7-M14</p> <p>Cross-fertilisation workshop (cross- pilots), kick-off Info Desk, open registration and collection of FAQs led by ZSI First meeting (remote) with MSF members</p> <p>3rd PHASE: COMMUNITY OF INTEREST M14-M42</p>		✓

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Co-analysis workshop (cross-pilot) Yearly meetings with MSF members Final meeting: contribution to a conference such as a roundtable	
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MSF Agenda Setting Meeting: MENTIMETER 2 RESULTS (15/05/24)
Participants: ZSI, SLG, ICONS, SLG, ICLEI, CARTIF, ICCS

Please anticipate: Participant's feedback to which of the below listed INHERIT topics could be beneficial for your task/WP in the first MSF event phase? Please vote:	Results
Cultural heritage in the context of... 1) social responsibility and social innovation 2) climate-smart and socially inclusive cultural management 3) the sustainable and sensitive valorisation of cultural heritage 4) innovation in retrofit 5) sustainability strategies and green technologies 6) benefits of the New European Bauhaus principles in praxis (i.e. as a practical approach in cultural heritage management)	social responsibility and social innovation innovation in retrofit sustainability strategies and green technologies benefits of the New European Bauhaus principles in praxis (i.e. as a practical approach in cultural heritage management)

Please anticipate: Participant's feedback to which of the below listed INHERIT topics could be beneficial for your task/WP in the first MSF event phase? Other: Please describe...

WP7 exploitation WP6 - We need mainly to get feedback on the capacity building processes and on learning formats. Furthermore, kind of "evaluation" understood as feedback rounds would be helpful for us. How can we prioritise the KPIs and pillars used in the assessment tool? on the development of the services WP3 to weight (prioritise) T3.2 pillars (assessment and monitoring method.) How each service can be implemented in practice to maximize its impact and generalise (large scale use) in terms of practices used and people or technologies involved

Please include a first question of interest linked to the selection of topic!

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How can the services be implemented to maximise their impact and generalise their use (large scale implementation) in terms e.g. of people and technologies involved
 Civil society organisations
 How do you think the NEB framework could be helpful in long-term cultural heritage transformation (in relation to the resource efficiency)?
 Prioritisation of KPIs and pillars to evaluate the CH building (related also to retrofitting strategies to be implemented in buildings > how to assess their benefits/ impact/ cost-effectiveness)

Who could give relevant answers to this question – please define the target group of participants (to build a working group)?	Results
Please vote: Civil society organisations CH practitioner Policy makers or admin Academia	Civil society organisations CH practitioner

Please specify discipline, field and potential network or organisation for your chosen target group/s:

cultural heritage + energy efficiency, mostly from the technical perspective, but combined with aesthetics
 retrofitting experts / companies
 architects and smart-building practitioners /engineers
 engineers, architects

9.4. User Story Template & Service Description Template

9.4.1. User Story Template

User Story ID	US [1.1]			
User Story Title	[title of your User Story]			
Pilot	[which pilot relates to this user story]			
Relevant Service(s)	[services that are related to the user story]			
Description	[describe how this service will help your pilot execute the desired results]			
Needs	[describe what are the needs addressed in the given scenario] <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Installation of sensors and monitoring system 2. Collecting and analysing the data collected 			
Potential Barriers	[describe potential barriers or challenges associated with the service]			
Equipment	[describe any relevant equipment that could be leveraged by the service]			
	Equipment	Short description		
	Equipment Name 1			
	Equipment Name 2			
	Equipment Name 3			
Datasets	[describe any relevant existing dataset that could be leveraged by the service; specify the formats, size, means of access]			
	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)
	Dataset Name 1			Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 2			
	Dataset Name 3			
	Dataset Name 4			
	Dataset Name 5			

9.4.2. Service Description Template

Service ID	
Service name	Interactive screen usage and AR-VR interfaces
Lead Partner	UCL
General Description	
General Description	General Description of the tool; Explain the motivation, goal and context of its use
Service Functionalities	
Input Data	Describe the input data requested by the service; Specify how this will be collected (open/pilot data etc.)

	Data Sets	Short description	Size	Data Diss. Level (Open or Private)	Means for data collection
	Dataset Name 1				
	Dataset Name 2				
	Dataset Name 3				
Output Data	Describe the output of the service and how the user is expected to interact with it.				
Service Workflow	Describe a sequence of steps to explain the inner logic of the service				
Internal architecture & Technologies used	<i>Please explain the functionality of the service, explain the subcomponents and the inner architecture of the service, and which technologies are used. Is the tool containerized (e.g., available as Docker image)?</i>				